

Milestone 2.1

REPORT ON SURVEY OF OPERATION OF NMR FACILITIES DURING THE PANDEMIC

of Remote NMR (R-NMR):

Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement N. 101058595

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Project acronym:	R-NMR
Project Title:	Remote NMR: Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities
Grant Agreement number:	10105859
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Project website address:	http://www.r-nmr.eu/
Milestone No.:	M2.1
Lead Beneficiary:	UOXF
Type and dissemination level:	Report - Public
Due Date:	M5 (30 November, 2022)
Delivery Date:	30 November 2022

History of Changes		
Version	Publication date	Changes
1.0	28.11.2022	Initial version
2.0	08.08.2023	Final version including an Executive Summary

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1. Executive Summary

An online survey of NMR facility managers was carried out in order to collect information about their experiences with remote NMR access during the pandemic. Responses were collected from 142 facility managers from 29 countries; 58% of the facilities provided some form of remote access. The detailed responses to a range of questions about instrumentation, software, userbase, mode of remote access and reasons for not providing remote access provide important insights into how the NMR community responded to the pandemic and will be a valuable resource in the development of remote access protocols within Work Packages 3 and 4. It is encouraging that ~70% of facilities not currently providing remote access would like to implement this once the R-NMR project has developed a standardized protocol. This confirms that there will be significant interest in the outcomes of the R-NMR project.

2. Background

This work has been carried out in the context of Task 2.1, Review of current protocols in place for remote access to NMR facilities, including statistics on current implementation.

In order to provide a detailed picture of the experience of NMR facilities during the pandemic, an online survey will be designed as a first goal of this work package and will be sent out to all European NMR facilities. This will include any possible information on the size and specific expertise of facility, degree of operation, adopted access modalities, problems encountered, perceived bottlenecks etc. The survey will be first circulated within the consortium and then sent out to the managers of NMR facilities in Europe and throughout the world.

The results of the survey will be collated and analysed to provide a picture of the protocols that have been implemented during the Covid-19 pandemic (M2.1). Selected NMR facilities will be invited based on interesting and novel procedures they have adopted or based on particular problems that they encountered.

3. Survey Implementation

The survey was designed in consultation with other WP2 partners. The survey was approved by the Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee (CUREC Reference

R77838/RE001) and implemented in the Jisc online survey software. The survey was open for 23 days. Potential participants in the survey were contacted in two ways. For some countries, R-NMR partners sent an email requesting participation in the survey to NMR facilities using national email lists (UK, Germany, France, Italy). For the remaining countries, facility manager email addresses were collected from R-NMR participants and by searching the internet for NMR facilities in specific countries. A copy of the survey, including the Participant Information Sheet, is available in Appendix 1.

4. Summary of NMR Facilities – Equipment/Software/Applications/User base

The survey was completed by 142 NMR facility managers. They represent NMR facilities in 29 countries (Question 3). The highest number of participants represented French NMR facilities (33 responses). More than ten responses were obtained from Germany (16), Italy (11), Portugal (11) and the United Kingdom (20). 41.5% of the responses were from national NMR infrastructures (Question 4). The first part of the survey included a range of questions about the NMR facilities; the survey results describing the 142 NMR facilities are included as Appendix 2. The responses were obtained from facilities with as few as a single NMR spectrometer to more than 15 spectrometers (Question 5). More than half of the facilities were equipped with 4 or more NMR spectrometers. The spectrometers ranged from Benchtop NMR to 1.2 GHz NMR spectrometers; 69% of the spectrometers at these facilities operate at 600MHz or lower (Question 6). More than 95% of the NMR facilities (135 of 142) were equipped with Bruker spectrometers but as many as 39 facilities also have spectrometers from other manufacturers (Agilent, JEOL, and Magritek Benchtop)(Question 7). The very high number of Bruker spectrometers running TopSpin in the NMR community justifies the majority of effort in Remote-NMR in the implementation of remote access to these Bruker systems. However, analysis of the survey responses from facilities providing remote access shows that this has been implemented on some Agilent/Varian systems. If time allows in the project, protocols for remote access to Agilent/Varian systems should be discussed with relevant stakeholders.

The Bruker spectrometers operate a range of TopSpin versions ranging from 1.3 to 4; the majority (64%) of facilities are running TopSpin 3 (Question 8). A significant number of the sites with Bruker spectrometers also run IconNMR (59 facilities in total). Linux is the most

common operating system for spectrometers (65.2% of facilities use Linux) with Windows a close second (53.2% of facilities use Windows)(Question 9). The most common Linux implementation is CentOS (a range of versions 2, 3, 5, 6, 7 and 10 in use). Windows versions XP, 7, 9, 10 and 11 are in use. The widespread use of both Linux and Windows and the large range of operating system versions in use may represent a challenge for the implementation of remote access; the older OS versions may not be as secure as required.

Solution-state NMR is the primary type of NMR for which facilities are equipped (57%). Only 6.3% of NMR facilities are primarily equipped for solid-state NMR and 36.6% are equipped for both solution and solid-state NMR (Question 10). The NMR facilities accommodate a range of users (Question 11). More than 80% of facilities have local departmental users and users from other departments in their Universities/Research facilities. Roughly 50% of facilities provide access for national users and almost 30% have transnational users (EU or world-wide). A large number of facilities (57.1%) have industrial users showing a strong link in the NMR community between academic and industrial organisations. The NMR facilities are used for a very wide range of studies ranging from NMR associated with undergraduate/graduate teaching, to routine characterisation of organic molecules, to biomolecular NMR, to metabolomics, materials science research, NMR of soft materials and method development (Question 12).

The NMR facilities have a range of userbases ranging from less than 25 users to more than 100 users per year (Question 13). Statistics about the number of local, national, transnational and industrial users have also been collected (Questions 14-17). Local users varied considerably between NMR facilities; 39.1% of facilities had up to 25 users, 26.3% of facilities have 26-50 users, 21.8% of facilities had 51-100 users and 12.8% of facilities had over 100 users. Facilities generally had fewer national, transnational and industrial users; in all three categories up to 25 users was the most common response.

Questions 18 to 22 addressed topics including: user login procedures, levels of user expertise and spectrometer access, and NMR data security. The most common user login mode is via a shared account with open access to other users' files (65.7%). A further 35% of facilities have individual accounts with no access to other users' files. Around 18% of facilities have other login methods including individual accounts with access to other users' data. The majority

(56.1%) of NMR facilities provide different levels of spectrometer access for users with different levels of expertise (Questions 19-20). Facility managers provided details information about how user expertise is assessed at their facilities (Question 21) and also on procedures for securing NMR data and for user access to data (Question 22). A detailed analysis of these responses will provide useful input for Work Packages 3 and 4 which will be defining a common procedure for remote access and measurement (specifically Task 3.2), and for remote control of instrumentation (specifically Tasks 4.3 and 4.4).

After these detailed questions about the NMR facilities, the facility managers were asked if their facility provided remote access to their NMR facility (Question 23). Remote access was defined in several ways: 1) direct remote access – users directly operate the NMR spectrometer by remote login to the NMR spectrometer computer; 2) assisted remote access – users communicate via a computer linkup (Zoom/Teams etc) or telephone with a local operator who controls the NMR spectrometer; 3) any other type of remote access. Around 58% of the facilities provided some type of remote access to NMR spectrometers during the pandemic and around 42% did not provide remote access. The responses to the questions that followed this are analysed according to whether remote access was or was not provided.

5. Responses from NMR Facilities Providing Remote Access

The survey results for the NMR facilities that provided remote access to NMR are included as Appendix 3. The majority of facilities providing remote access (83.1%) provided direct remote access (57.8%) or both direct and assisted remote access (25.3%). Most respondents provided additional detail about their provision of remote access. Facilities providing remote access were asked to answer further questions relating to their provision of remote access (Questions 25 to 43). The majority of remote access has been provided on Bruker spectrometers (97.3%) (Question 31). Nearly all facilities provided remote access for local users. Almost 30% of these facilities also provided remote access for national users with a smaller number providing access for transnational or industrial users. The number of remote users has been relatively small with 63.5% of facilities having only up to 10 remote users. Development of a common remote access protocol and the provision of training for users and facility managers should lead to an increase in the numbers of remote users.

During the preparation of the R-NMR grant application, the project partners had identified AnyDesk, NoMachine (NX) and TeamViewer as software they had used for remote access. These three software packages were used by many NMR facilities but, interestingly, the survey showed that a number of other packages were used to provide remote access. These include DWService, VNC, FastViewer, Splashtop, and Guacamole. These other software packages will need to be investigated in WP2, WP3 and WP4 in order to assess their usefulness for remote access. The advantages and disadvantages of these software packages may be one area to investigate further in the one-to-one online interviews with some facility managers that are planned for December/January.

At most facilities, local IT staff placed some restrictions on remote user access which included registration for a local computer account and/or VPN access (Question 33). In some cases, NMR facility managers did not consult local IT staff because they were worried they might say no to remote access. In designing a remote access protocol in WP 3 and 4, it will be important to consider IT security questions and to work with local IT staff to ensure a secure system is designed. In most facilities the login procedures for on-site and remote users were the same (Question 34). Remote users were provided with support from local staff at 68.9% of NMR facilities (Question 35). This assistance was fairly uniformly divided between assistance with sample preparation, with sample loading, with setup of NMR experiments, and with data transfer. Almost half of the respondents indicated that the availability of automated sample changes (such as Bruker SampleCase and SampleJet) was important for the provision of remote access (Question 37). Remote access was only possible for certain user types at 83.3% of NMR facilities (Question 38). This information, and the detailed answers provided, will inform Tasks 3.2 and 4.4 of WP3 and WP4. Respondents also provided details about how NMR data collected by remote users was protected (Question 39) which will provide useful input for Task 4.3 of WP4. Finally, facility managers were asked about bottlenecks that they encountered in provision of remote NMR (Question 40) and for any other information that they wanted to provide (Question 43). These responses will assist in development of common protocols for remote access as they highlight a range of problems that have already been encountered. It is very encouraging to see that 94.6% of the NMR facilities that provided remote access during the pandemic have continue to do so even after ‘pandemic’ restrictions have been lifted (Question 42).

6. Responses from NMR Facilities With No Remote Access

The survey results for the NMR facilities that did not provide remote access to NMR are included as Appendix 4. Several reasons were given for not providing remote access (Question 23b). The most common reasons were 1) no demand from users for remote access and 2) IT security concerns making remote access impossible. A smaller number of respondents said remote access was not needed because there were no restrictions during the pandemic restricting in-person access (12 responses from the following countries - Germany 5, Portugal 3, Italy 2, Latvia 1, Austria 1). Respondents were also invited to give more detailed information about reasons for not providing remote access. Analysis of these responses will provide valuable insights about how the R-NMR project can make remote NMR access easier for these sites to implement. Encouragingly, 70% of the sites not providing remote access indicated that they would be interested in implementing this once R-NMR has developed a standardized protocol. This confirms that there will be significant interest in the outcomes of the R-NMR project.

7. Final Comments and Next Steps

At the end of the survey, respondents were given the opportunity to provide their name/email address if they were willing to provide more detailed information via a one-to-one online interview; more than 50% of the respondents agreed to do this. Once the detailed responses to the survey have been analysed in detail by R-NMR partners engaged in Work Packages 2, 3 and 4, individuals who have provided particularly interesting responses will be contacted, if they have consented to this, for a more detailed discussion. This additional information will feed into WP3 and WP4. In the next 2 months, a larger survey of users of NMR facilities will be conducted (Task 2.2). This will focus on the users' experiences of remote access and ask for ways in which user needs and the user experience can be improved. This survey will also ask questions about how user samples are transported to the NMR facility.

APPENDIX 1

Remote-NMR (R-NMR): Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities

NMR FACILITY MANAGER SURVEY (2-24 November 2022)

Univ. of Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee Approval Reference: [R77838/RE001]

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET AND SURVEY

Remote-NMR (R-NMR): Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Central University Research Ethics Committee Approval Reference: [R77838/RE001]

1. *Introductory paragraph*

Prior to the Covid19 pandemic, the overwhelming majority of NMR data collection was conducted by scientists traveling to local, national and transnational NMR facilities and sitting directly in front of the NMR console to setup data collection. The experiments were often set up together with experienced staff to ensure sample integrity, best conduct of experiments, interactive planning and peer teaching, and initial analysis of acquired data to assess the correct outcome of the experiments. Due to the lockdown restrictions in many countries during 2020-2021, this scenario had to change dramatically. The experiences of several European NMR facilities during the Covid19 pandemic have shown that remote access is feasible within the field of NMR spectroscopy. It is the aim of the Remote-NMR project to develop and exploit this type of access in full.

You are being invited to take part in the R-NMR project because you are a manager of an NMR facility. Before you decide to participate in the survey, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether you wish to take part.

2. *Why is this research being conducted?*

Remote access to NMR spectrometers has been implemented successfully at several NMR facilities around the EU/UK during the Covid19 pandemic. The R-NMR project is being conducted in order to collect information from NMR facility managers about their NMR facilities and about their experiences with remote access so that a common protocol for remote access for all facilities can be developed and adopted by facilities across the EU/UK.

3. Why have I been invited to take part?

You have been invited to complete a survey because you have been identified as a manager of an NMR facility. Some NMR facility managers who have completed the survey and have agreed to provide further information will also be invited to participate in a one-to-one online interview.

4. Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. You can withdraw yourself from the study, without giving a reason, by advising me of this decision. The deadline by which you can withdraw any information you have contributed to the research is 31 December 2023; any data that you have provided will be deleted.

5. What will happen to me if I take part in the research?

You will be invited to complete an online survey. The survey is aimed at NMR facility managers and will ask questions about the NMR facility you manage, your experiences with remote access to NMR spectrometers and for your views on how remote access can be improved in the future.

The survey can be completed without providing your name or contact email address but you will be asked to indicate in which country your NMR facility is located. There will be the option to provide more detailed information via a one-to-one online interview. If you are interested, you will be asked to provide your name/email address so that you can be contacted directly. You are not obliged to take part in an online interview if contacted.

6. What are the possible disadvantages and risks in taking part?

There are no disadvantages or risks in taking part in this research except that you will need to spend some time completing the surveys (up to 30 minutes) and possibly provide additional help to the R-NMR project by having an online interview about your experiences (~30 minutes and up to an hour).

7. Are there any benefits in taking part?

The benefits to you and to the wider NMR community by taking part in this project will be the improvement of remote NMR access across the EU/UK that will be the outcome of the R-NMR project.

8. What information will be collected and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research objectives?

We will not collect any information that will directly identify you, unless you provide your name and contact email address at the end of the survey. In this case your name/email address will be associated with the responses that you have made to the survey and to the information provided during the online interview. Your name/email address will only be accessible to Prof Christina Redfield and will be deleted at the end of the project (30 June 2025) or at the end of your participation in the study (if you withdraw before 31 December 2023). Information that all participants provide about their NMR facility and their experiences with remote access will be included in discussions with other R-NMR participants and included in reports but this information will not be associated with your name or your email address. Your IP address will not be collected.

All survey data and interview consent forms will be stored in Oxford on a secure desktop computer (password protected and behind a firewall) during the duration of the R-NMR project (until 30 June 2025). A non-identifiable version of the survey (with any name/email information) will be created for longer-term storage on University servers. We intend to keep this version of the survey and all interview consent forms for 3 years beyond publication of the project.

9. Will the research be published? Could I be identified from any publications or other research outputs?

The findings from the NMR facility manager surveys/interviews being carried out online by Oxford researchers as part of the R-NMR research project will be used in a report about the current protocols in place for remote access to NMR spectrometers. This report will be circulated to other R-NMR grant participants and will be used as the starting point for other work packages in R-NMR. Individual will not be identified in any of these reports. It is very unlikely that the outcomes of the surveys/ interviews being carried out online by Oxford researchers will be written up for publication.

10. Data Protection

The University of Oxford is the data controller with respect to your personal data, and as such will determine how your personal data is used in the study. The University will process your personal data for the purpose of the research outlined above. Research is a task that is performed in the public interest. Further information about your rights with respect to your personal data is available at <https://compliance.admin.ox.ac.uk/individual-rights>.

11. Who is funding the research?

Remote-NMR is funded by a grant from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058595. Participation by U.K. partners, including the University of Oxford, is funded via the Horizon Europe Guarantee scheme run by Innovate UK, part of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

12. Who has reviewed this study?

This study has received ethics approval from a subcommittee of the University of Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee. (Ethics reference: R77838/RE001).

The surveys have also been approved by the Steering Board of the Remote-NMR project.

13. Who do I contact if I have a concern about the research or I wish to complain?

If you have a concern about any aspect of this study, please contact Professor Christina Redfield (see contact details in next section), and she will do her best to answer your query. I will acknowledge your concern within 10 working days and give you an indication of how it will be dealt with. If you remain unhappy or wish to make a formal complaint, please contact the Chair of the Research Ethics Committee at the University of Oxford who will seek to resolve the matter as soon as possible:

The Chair, Medical Sciences Interdivisional Research Ethics Committee;
Email: ethics@medsci.ox.ac.uk; Address: Research Services, University of Oxford, Boundary Brook House, Churchill Drive, Headington, Oxford OX3 7GB

14. Further Information and Contact Details

If you would like to discuss the research with someone beforehand (or if you have questions afterwards), please contact:

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Oxford OX1 3QU, U.K.
University tel: +44 1865 275330
University email: christina.redfield@bioch.ox.ac.uk

Remote-NMR: NMR Facility Manager Survey

INTRODUCTION

Remote-NMR (R-NMR): Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities

Prior to the Covid19 pandemic, the overwhelming majority of NMR data collection was carried out in-person at the NMR facility. Due to the lockdown restrictions in many countries during 2020-2021, this scenario had to change dramatically. Our experiences during Covid19 show that remote access is feasible within the field of NMR spectroscopy, and it is the aim of the Remote-NMR project (R-NMR) to develop and exploit this type of access in full.

The purpose of this survey is to collect information from NMR facility managers about their NMR facilities and their experiences of providing remote access to their NMR spectrometers. A separate survey, aimed specifically at *users* of NMR facilities, will be launched later in 2022.

Before you decide to participate in this survey, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what will be done with your responses to the survey. Please take time to read the information in the Participant Information Sheet that can be accessed at ([Click Here](#)). Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

PRIVACY NOTICE AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN THE SURVEY

You are invited to complete this online survey aimed at NMR facility managers. We will ask questions about your NMR facility, your experiences with providing remote access to NMR spectrometers and for your views on how remote access can be improved in the future. The survey can be completed without providing your name or contact email address but you will be asked to indicate in which country your NMR facility is located. There will be the option to provide more detailed information via a one-to-one online interview; in this case you will be asked to provide your name/email address so that you can be contacted directly. Information that you provide about your experiences with remote access will be included in discussions with other R-NMR project participants and in project reports; however this information **will not** be associated with your name or your email address. All survey data will be stored at the University of Oxford on a secure computer (password protected and behind a firewall) during the duration of the R-NMR project (until 30 June 2025). An anonymised version of the survey (without any name/email information) will be created for longer-term storage. We intend to keep this version for 3 years after publication of the outcome of the project. Please confirm below: That you have read this information, and if you require further detailed information, that you have read the Participant Information Sheet. That you understand who will have access to any personal data that you provide, how data will be stored and what will happen to data at the end of the project. That you understand how to raise a concern or make a complaint. That you are willing to continue with the survey. * *Required*

Yes

No

INFORMATION ABOUT YOUR NMR FACILITY

Please confirm that you are the manager of an NMR facility. (Please try to ensure that the survey is only completed by one person involved in the management of your NMR facility). * *Required*

- Yes No

In which country is your NMR facility located? Select one: * *Required*

- | | | |
|-----------------------------------|-----------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Austria | <input type="radio"/> Belgium | <input type="radio"/> Bulgaria |
| <input type="radio"/> Croatia | <input type="radio"/> Cyprus | <input type="radio"/> Czech Republic |
| <input type="radio"/> Denmark | <input type="radio"/> Estonia | <input type="radio"/> Finland |
| <input type="radio"/> France | <input type="radio"/> Germany | <input type="radio"/> Greece |
| <input type="radio"/> Hungary | <input type="radio"/> Iceland | <input type="radio"/> Ireland |
| <input type="radio"/> Israel | <input type="radio"/> Italy | <input type="radio"/> Latvia |
| <input type="radio"/> Lithuania | <input type="radio"/> Luxembourg | <input type="radio"/> Malta |
| <input type="radio"/> Netherlands | <input type="radio"/> Norway | <input type="radio"/> Poland |
| <input type="radio"/> Portugal | <input type="radio"/> Romania | <input type="radio"/> Serbia |
| <input type="radio"/> Slovakia | <input type="radio"/> Slovenia | <input type="radio"/> Spain |
| <input type="radio"/> Sweden | <input type="radio"/> Switzerland | <input type="radio"/> United Kingdom |
| <input type="radio"/> Ukraine | <input type="radio"/> Other | |

If you selected Other, please specify:

Is your NMR facility part of a national infrastructure? * *Required*

- Yes No

INFORMATION ABOUT YOUR NMR FACILITY

How many spectrometers do you have in your NMR facility? *Optional*

- | | | |
|-----------------------------|---------------------------|---------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> 1 | <input type="radio"/> 2 | <input type="radio"/> 3 |
| <input type="radio"/> 4 | <input type="radio"/> 5 | <input type="radio"/> 6-9 |
| <input type="radio"/> 10-15 | <input type="radio"/> >15 | |

At what ^1H frequencies do your spectrometers operate? (select all that apply) *Optional*

- | | | |
|---|----------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 400 MHz or lower | <input type="checkbox"/> 500 MHz | <input type="checkbox"/> 600 MHz |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 700 MHz | <input type="checkbox"/> 750 MHz | <input type="checkbox"/> 800 MHz |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 850 MHz | <input type="checkbox"/> 900 MHz | <input type="checkbox"/> 950 MHz |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1 GHz | <input type="checkbox"/> 1.1 GHz | <input type="checkbox"/> 1.2 GHz |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Benchtop NMR | | |

What type of spectrometers do you have in your facility? (select all that apply) *Optional*

- | | | |
|---------------------------------|---|-------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bruker | <input type="checkbox"/> Agilent/Varian | <input type="checkbox"/> JEOL |
| <input type="checkbox"/> GE | <input type="checkbox"/> Other | |

If you selected Other, please specify:

What data acquisition software do your spectrometers run? (select all that apply)

Optional

<input type="checkbox"/> Bruker TopSpin	<input type="checkbox"/> Bruker IconNMR	<input type="checkbox"/> Agilent VnmrJ
<input type="checkbox"/> JEOL Delta	<input type="checkbox"/> GE/Omega	<input type="checkbox"/> Other

If you selected Bruker TopSpin, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

If you selected Bruker IconNMR, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

If you selected Agilent VnmrJ, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

If you selected JEOL Delta, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

If you selected GE/Omega, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

If you selected Other, please specify the software name and version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

What operating systems do your spectrometer computers run? (select all that apply)
Optional

- Linux Windows Mac OS
 Other

If you selected Linux, please specify the distribution (Debian, Fedora etc) and version.

If you selected Windows, please specify the version.

If you selected Mac OS, please specify the version.

If you selected Other, please specify the operating system and version.

INFORMATION ABOUT YOUR NMR FACILITY

What type of NMR are the spectrometers in your facility equipped for? (select one)

Optional

- Primarily solution-state NMR Primarily solid-state NMR Both solution- and solid-state NMR

Tell us about the users of your NMR facility. (select all that apply) *Optional*

- Local departmental users
 Users from multiple departments in your university/research centre
 National users
 Transnational users (EU-wide or world-wide)
 Industrial users

What types of NMR experiments do your users carry out? (select all that apply) *Optional*

- NMR associated with undergraduate/graduate teaching
 Routine small molecule characterization supporting organic chemistry
 Biomolecular NMR research
 Metabolomics research
 Micro-imaging research
 Materials Science NMR research
 Other Physical Sciences NMR research
 Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

INFORMATION ABOUT YOUR NMR FACILITY

On average, how many users does your facility have in a year? *Optional*

- 1-25 26-50 51-100
 >100

Approximately how many users do you have in each of the following categories?

Local users

National users

Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide)

Industrial users

INFORMATION ABOUT YOUR NMR FACILITY

How do users of your NMR facility login to the spectrometers and do they have access to other users' data? (select all that apply) *Optional*

- Individual accounts with no access to other users' files
- Shared account with open access to other users' files
- Short-term login account with no access to other users' files (usernames are recycled)
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

Are different levels of spectrometer access provided for users with different levels of expertise? *Optional*

- Yes No

Which of the following describe categories of users in your facility? (select all that apply)
Optional

- Non-expert users (can select from a limited list of experiments and parameters)
- Standard users (can select from a wider list of experiments but cannot run their own

pulse sequences)

- Expert users (can run any experiments and write their own pulse sequences)
- No distinction is made between user types
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

If your facility has different categories of users, how is user expertise level assessed? (Please specify)

How is user NMR data kept secure and how do users access their data? (Please specify).
Optional

EXPERIENCE WITH REMOTE ACCESS TO YOUR NMR FACILITY

Prior to, during and since the Covid19 pandemic, did you provide remote access to one or more of the NMR spectrometers in your facility? By remote access, we mean that either: 1) users could directly operate the NMR spectrometer by remote login to the NMR spectrometer computer (direct remote access), or 2) users could communicate via a computer linkup (Zoom/Teams etc) or telephone with a local operator who controlled the NMR spectrometer based on the information provided by the remote user (assisted remote access), or 3) some other type of remote access. * Required

<input type="radio"/> Yes - direct remote access.	<input type="radio"/> Yes – assisted remote access.	<input type="radio"/> Yes – both direct and assisted remote access.
<input type="radio"/> Yes - another type of remote access (please specify below)	<input type="radio"/> No	

If you would like to provide more detailed information about your mode of remote spectrometer access then please fill in the text box.

Why has remote access to spectrometers not been implemented in your facility? (select any that apply)

<input type="checkbox"/> No demand for remote access from users.
<input type="checkbox"/> There were no restrictions during the pandemic that prevented onsite use of spectrometers.
<input type="checkbox"/> Too difficult to implement remote access.

- IT security concerns made remote access impossible.
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

The aim of the Remote-NMR project is to develop a common framework for remote spectrometer access taking into account best practice across the EU/UK. Standardized training for remote access will also be put in place. Once this has been completed, would your NMR facility be interested in implementing remote spectrometer access?

- Yes No

If your facility has provided any type of remote access then select 'Yes' to proceed to further questions about your implementation of remote access. If your facility has not provided any type of remote access then select 'No' to proceed to the end of the survey.

- Yes No

EXPERIENCE WITH REMOTE ACCESS TO YOUR NMR FACILITY

If you have provided remote access, what categories of users had remote access. (please select all that apply)

- Local users
- National users
- Transnational users (EU-wide or world-wide)
- Industrial users

Overall, how many remote users has your facility had in the last 2-3 years?

- 1-10 11-20 >20

How many remote users did you have in each of the following categories?

Local users

National users

Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide)

Industrial users

What type of spectrometers were available for remote access? (select all that apply)

- Bruker Agilent/Varian JEOL
 GE Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

What software was used for remote access? (select all that apply)

- AnyDesk NoMachine (NX) TeamViewer
 Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

EXPERIENCE WITH REMOTE ACCESS TO YOUR NMR FACILITY

Did local IT staff place any restrictions on remote user access to ensure network security (select all that apply)?

- Registration for local computer account required?
- VPN access required?
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

Did login procedures for remote users differ from those for on-site users?

- Yes
- No

If yes, how did remote users login?

- Individual accounts with no access to other users' files
- Shared account with open access to other users' files
- Short-term login account with no access to other users' files (usernames are recycled)
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

Were remote users provided with support by local NMR facility staff?

Yes No

If yes, what type of support was provided? (select all that apply)

- Assistance with sample preparation (from sample material shipped to facility)
- Assistance with loading NMR samples into spectrometers
- Assistance with setup of NMR experiments
- Assistance with data transfer
- Telephone/email assistance in case of problems
- Website/YouTube videos explaining how to use remote access
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

EXPERIENCE WITH REMOTE ACCESS TO YOUR NMR FACILITY

How were users' NMR samples loaded into spectrometers? (select all that apply)

- Users put their own samples in the spectrometer and then left the facility to operate the spectrometer remotely.
- Facility staff loaded NMR samples left by users at a drop-off point into the spectrometer.
- Users shipped samples in NMR tubes or rotors to the facility via post/courier and facility staff loaded these NMR samples into the spectrometer.
- Users shipped samples to the facility via post/courier and facility staff loaded the samples into NMR tubes or rotors prior to putting the samples into the spectrometer.
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

Are spectrometers available for remote access equipped with automatic sample changers and were these important for provision of remote access?

- Yes automated sample changers available.
- Yes automated sample changers available and important for provision of remote access.
- No sample changers were available.

If yes, please indicate the make/model of sample changer.

If yes, was the sample changer temperature controlled (i.e. are samples stored at a specified temperature before insertion in the spectrometer)?

- Yes No

Was remote access restricted to users with specific levels of expertise or were all user categories able to access spectrometers remotely?

- Yes, remote access only possible for certain user types. No, all user types were allowed to use remote access.

If remote access was restricted to users with specific levels of expertise then please specify which category(ies) of users?

How was the NMR data collected by remote users protected and/or kept secure and did the procedures differ from those in place for on-site users? (please specify)

EXPERIENCE WITH REMOTE ACCESS TO YOUR NMR FACILITY

What bottlenecks or other problems did you identify in providing remote spectrometer access?

If your facility has a webpage with information about remote access please enter the URL below.

Is your facility continuing to provide remote access to NMR spectrometers now that some/many/all 'pandemic' restrictions have been lifted?

Yes

No

FINAL QUESTIONS

If you have further information that you would like to provide, please enter this in the text box below.

Are you willing to be contacted for more information about your NMR facility and/or about the provision of remote access in your NMR facility? This would be via an online one-to-one interview.

Yes No

Consent - If you agree to be interviewed online you will be asked at the start of the interview for your verbal consent and a written record of this will be made. The form will then be signed by Professor Christina Redfield, scanned and emailed in a password-protected copy to you for your records. A copy of this written consent form will be kept in a secure online location. Please indicate below that "I agree for you to contact me with a view to obtaining further information for this research. I understand that my contact details will be held only for the purposes of this research. If I am contacted, I am under no obligation to take part."

Yes No

Please fill in your name and email address in the text box below.

FINAL COMMENTS AND THANKS!

Thank you very much for taking the time to complete this survey. Your responses will be important in formulating common practices for future provision of remote access to NMR spectrometers.

If you would like further information about the R-NMR project then please visit the project webpage at <https://www.r-nmr.eu> or follow the project on Twitter @RemoteNMR_eu. A summary of the results of the survey will be available on the R-NMR web site in early 2023.

APPENDIX 2

Remote-NMR (R-NMR): Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities

NMR FACILITY MANAGER SURVEY (2-24 November 2022)

Univ. of Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee Approval Reference: [R77838/RE001]

SUMMARY OF RESPONSES FROM ALL NMR FACILITIES

Introduction

Lockdown restrictions in many countries during 2020-2021 Covid19 pandemic resulted in the implementation of remote access to NMR spectrometers as a way of enabling the continuation of important research. The experiences of several European NMR facilities during the pandemic have shown that this access mode can work well within the field of NMR spectroscopy. It is the aim of the Remote-NMR project to develop and exploit remote access to NMR facilities. Work Package 2 within R-NMR focusses on the “Remote NMR Landscape”. Task 2.1 within WP2 is a review of current protocols in place for remote access to NMR facilities, including statistics on current implementation of remote access. This information has been collected via an online survey of NMR facility managers.

This document is a summary of the responses from all of the 142 NMR facility managers who completed the survey. Responses for questions relating to the NMR facilities are included (up to and including questions 23).

Some of the questions allowed responses in text boxes. The responses have been input into Excel and analysed within Excel; the results are summarised below.

Question 8 a-f asked about the version of NMR data acquisition software run on NMR facility spectrometers.

8a – Bruker TopSpin – 95.7% of NMR facilities use Bruker TopSpin on at least one NMR spectrometer. Versions ranging from TopSpin 1.3 to TopSpin 4 were indicated in the survey responses. More than one version of TopSpin was in use at many facilities; there were 172 entries in total.

TopSpin version 1 or 2 – 17.4% ; TopSpin version 3 – 64.0% ; TopSpin version 4 – 18.6%

Within TopSpin 3, ~50% of facilities used either version 3.5 (15.1%) or version 3.6 (34.9%)

8b – Bruker IconNMR – Versions 3, 4 and 5 of IconNMR were indicated in the survey responses. More than one version of IconNMR was in use at many facilities; there were 60 entries in total.

IconNMR version 3 – 5% ; IconNMR version 4 – 33.3% ; IconNMR version 5 – 61.7%

Within IconNMR 5, 59.5% of facilities use version 5.0, 10.8% use 5.1 and 29.7% use 5.2

Question 9 a/b asked about the version of Linux/Window operating system used on NMR facility spectrometers. Linux is used on at least one NMR spectrometer in 65.2% of NMR facilities, while Windows is used on at least one NMR spectrometer in 53.2% of NMR facilities.

9a – Linux distribution and version – CentOS is used on 88.1% of NMR facilities; this is the version of Linux that is distributed by Bruker. CentOS versions ranging from 2 to 10 were specified. A small number of responses indicated Fedora, Debian and Ubuntu.

24.7% of responses did not specify a version of CentOS

1.1% of responses specified version 2

1.1% of responses specified version 3

22.5% of responses specified version 5

1.1% of responses specified version 6

48.3% of responses specified version 7

1.1% of responses specified version 10

9b – Windows – Versions XP, 7, 9, 10 and 11 were specified in responses.

14.3% of responses specified XP

29.9% of responses specified version 7

1.3% of responses specified version 9

50.6% of responses specified version 10

3.9% of responses specified version 11

Questions 14-17 asked about the distribution of users between: Local users, National users, Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide, Industrial users. The breakdown of users was as follows.

14 - Local users:

0 0.0%

1-25 39.1%

26-50 26.3%

51-100 21.8%

>100 12.8%

15 – National users:

0 15.2%

1-25 79.0%

26-50 3.8%

51-100 1.9%

16 – Transnational users:

0 43.6%

1-25 53.8%

26-50 2.6%

17 – Industrial users:

0 15.1%

1-25 84.0%

26-50 0.9%

Remote-NMR: NMR Facility Manager Survey

Showing 142 of 142 responses

Showing **all** responses

Hiding **21** questions

Response rate: 71%

- 1** You are invited to complete this online survey aimed at NMR facility managers. We will ask questions about your NMR facility, your experiences with providing remote access to NMR spectrometers and for your views on how remote access can be improved in the future. The survey can be completed without providing your name or contact email address but you will be asked to indicate in which country your NMR facility is located. There will be the option to provide more detailed information via a one-to-one online interview; in this case you will be asked to provide your name/email address so that you can be contacted directly. Information that you provide about your experiences with remote access will be included in discussions with other R-NMR project participants and in project reports; however this information will not be associated with your name or your email address. All survey data will be stored at the University of Oxford on a secure computer (password protected and behind a firewall) during the duration of the R-NMR project (until 30 June 2025). An anonymised version of the survey (without any name/email information) will be created for longer-term storage. We intend to keep this version for 3 years after publication of the outcome of the project. Please confirm below: That you have read this information, and if you require further detailed information, that you have read the Participant Information Sheet. That you understand who will have access to any personal data that you provide, how data will be stored and what will happen to data at the end of the project. That you understand how to raise a concern or make a complaint. That you are willing to continue with the survey.

Yes 142 (100%)
No | 0

- 2** Please confirm that you are the manager of an NMR facility. (Please try to ensure that the survey is only completed by one person involved in the management of your NMR facility).

Yes 142 (100%)
No | 0

- 3** In which country is your NMR facility located? Select one:

3.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 2 responses	
Australia	951912-951894-101605905
Canada	951912-951894-101613960

4 Is your NMR facility part of a national infrastructure?

5 How many spectrometers do you have in your NMR facility?

6 At what ¹H frequencies do your spectrometers operate? (select all that apply)

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

7 What type of spectrometers do you have in your facility? (select all that apply)

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

7.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 11 responses	
Magritek Benchtop	951912-951894-101369602
Stelar FFC relaxometer 200MHz with RS2D console	951912-951894-101613468
Magritech	951912-951894-101614904
Magritek	951912-951894-101644910
RS2D	951912-951894-101648927
Magritek	951912-951894-101742975
Nanalysis benchtop	951912-951894-101745527
Magritek RS2D	951912-951894-101768538
Home build/developed fast field cycling relaxometer	951912-951894-102073777
Magritek	951912-951894-102109484
Pure Devices	951912-951894-102130642

8 What data acquisition software do your spectrometers run? (select all that apply)

8.a If you selected Bruker TopSpin, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 129 responses	
3.6.2	951912-951894-101360820
3.5 4.1	951912-951894-101369358
1.3 3.2 3.5.6 3.6.1 4.1.3	951912-951894-101369602
TS3.6.x TS1.3	951912-951894-101370884
4.1.1	951912-951894-101372382

8.b If you selected Bruker IconNMR, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 42 responses	
4.0.7 4.7.7 5.0.6 5.0.9 5.2.3.1	951912-951894-101369602
5.0.12 4.7.7	951912-951894-101376470
5	951912-951894-101397499
5.0.11 and 5.2.4	951912-951894-101445018
3.6.5 4.1.4	951912-951894-101559699

8.c If you selected Agilent Vnmrj, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 17 responses	
openVnmrj	951912-951894-101550127
4.2	951912-951894-101644910
OpenVnmrj 2.1A	951912-951894-101675332
OpenVnmrj 3.1	951912-951894-101709365
Vnmrj 3.2	951912-951894-101713028

8.d If you selected JEOL Delta, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 6 responses	
5.3.1	951912-951894-101411307
Delta 5.X Delta 5.X	951912-951894-101550127
5.2	951912-951894-101642396
Delta 5.3.1	951912-951894-101644803
Jeol Delta v6.2	951912-951894-102074887

8.e If you selected GE/Omega, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

No responses

8.f If you selected Other, please specify the software name and version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing all 10 responses	
RS2D Spinit Stelar FFC software	951912-951894-101613468
Spinsolve	951912-951894-101614904
Magritek Spinsolve	951912-951894-101644910
SpinIt	951912-951894-101648927
SpinSight	951912-951894-101737673
Spinsolve Expert (Magritek) SpinIt (RS2D)	951912-951894-101768538
Bruker paravision 6	951912-951894-101783128
Home developed based on Matlab	951912-951894-102073777
Bruker ParaVision	951912-951894-102109484
Paravision360 v3.3	951912-951894-102130642

9 What operating systems do your spectrometer computers run? (select all that apply)

9.a If you selected Linux, please specify the distribution (Debian, Fedora etc) and version.

Showing first 5 of 84 responses	
CentOS	951912-951894-101369358
CentOS 5 and 7	951912-951894-101369602
CentOS	951912-951894-101370884
CentOS 7	951912-951894-101376470
CentOS 7.9	951912-951894-101376176

9.b If you selected Windows, please specify the version.

Showing first 5 of 65 responses	
10	951912-951894-101360820
WinXP	951912-951894-101370884
10	951912-951894-101372382
Win10 pro 21H1	951912-951894-101376176
XP Windows7 Windows9	951912-951894-101397329

9.c If you selected Mac OS, please specify the version.

Showing 1 response	
Monterey, Ventura	951912-951894-101614904

9.d If you selected Other, please specify the operating system and version.

Showing all 2 responses	
Sun Microsystems	951912-951894-101737673
Centos	951912-951894-102079790

10 What type of NMR are the spectrometers in your facility equipped for? (select one)

11 Tell us about the users of your NMR facility. (select all that apply)

12 What types of NMR experiments do your users carry out? (select all that apply)

12.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 16 responses	
Work that would fall under the NERC remit (soils, mineralogical samples, etc.).	951912-951894-101360820
De novo structure elucidation	951912-951894-101577839
polymer	951912-951894-101617105
Methodology development (hyperpolarization) and equipment development (probes)	951912-951894-101709365
NMR of soft materials (gels, ionic liquids, deep eutectic solvents, polymers) HP-NMR	951912-951894-101690708
Relaxometry, diffusometry	951912-951894-101783128
Metabolic tracing research	951912-951894-101849988
Reaction monitoring Molecular dynamics studies	951912-951894-101908122
complex mixtures	951912-951894-101953004
Routine small molecule char. for inorganic and physical chemistry, metal organic chemistry	951912-951894-101968664
Hyperpolarization experiments using pH2 and DNP	951912-951894-102075878
Natural Product chemistry Glycochemistry Fluorine compounds (19F-QCI 600MHz probe) 13C NMR (TXO probe, 700MHz) High pressure NMR (daedalus -> 3kbar)	951912-951894-102093469
soft matter analyses wit a HR MAS probe	951912-951894-102133983
pharmaceutical analysis	951912-951894-102138055
Natural Product chemistry (600MHz equipped with a microprobe) Glycochemistry	951912-951894-102118767
NMR in oriented media	951912-951894-102194221

13 On average, how many users does your facility have in a year?

14 Local users

Showing first 5 of 133 responses	
5 PIs	951912-951894-101360820
50	951912-951894-101369358
51-100	951912-951894-101369602
30	951912-951894-101372382
200	951912-951894-101376470

15 National users

Showing first 5 of 105 responses	
3 PIs	951912-951894-101360820
4	951912-951894-101369358
5	951912-951894-101372382
0	951912-951894-101376176
5	951912-951894-101397329

16 Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide)

Showing first 5 of 78 responses	
1-2 PIs	951912-951894-101360820
0	951912-951894-101372382
0	951912-951894-101376176
0	951912-951894-101397329
0	951912-951894-101509032

17 Industrial users

Showing first 5 of 106 responses	
0-1 Organisations	951912-951894-101360820
4	951912-951894-101369358
10	951912-951894-101369602
0	951912-951894-101372382
10	951912-951894-101376470

18 How do users of your NMR facility login to the spectrometers and do they have access to other users' data? (select all that apply)

18.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 25 responses	
Solid-state NMR research group users can access the shared login for running experiments and viewing data. Other users submit samples which are run by the facility manager, who then emails out a link to their data in a zip file on Dropbox.	951912-951894-101360820
Individual accounts with access to other users' files	951912-951894-101376176
Measurements are performed by the staff	951912-951894-101509032
Individual accounts with access to other users' files	951912-951894-101524313
Individual accounts with access to others files controlled by UNIX permissions	951912-951894-101603924
>Shared account amongst research group users- data not shared with other research groups >Open-access - no login required.	951912-951894-101605905
individual accounts and access to other users' files	951912-951894-101613305

Group of users (team of researchers) without access to other groups	951912-951894-101614904
Individual accounts with open access to other users' files within the same research group, read only access to other files.	951912-951894-101640129
Individual Accounts with access to other's files with an option for a sequestered environment if needed.	951912-951894-101737673
industrial: personal departmental: per institute for paranoid people we sometimes make individual accounts lab course account for training students separate user accounts within IconNMR	951912-951894-101742975
Individual accounts with limited access to other users' files	951912-951894-101745973
Individual accounts with possible access to other users' files depending on permissions set by account owners. Users can share data/files if they choose to. Account holders can belong to specific groups and decide who they share files with.	951912-951894-101849988
We use in house developed NMR data management system. https://www.nomad-nmr.uk/	951912-951894-101890690
Individual accounts with limited access to other user's files	951912-951894-101518991
Individual accounts with access to other users' files in read only mode	951912-951894-101957336
Individual accounts for research groups, all users of the same group share the account and have open access to the files of the group members but no access to the data of other research groups	951912-951894-101968664
For non-local users we only provide short-term login accounts.	951912-951894-101902953
group accounts: each research unit has its own account. Users of a same research unit can access the group data	951912-951894-102045678
Solution state: open access with shared Windows perma-login, but individual accounts in IconNMR. Users can see other users' files. Solids: individual Linux accounts, and users cannot access other users' files	951912-951894-102051473
Users from the same group account can submit samples on that account on the spectrometer but access to the same account users' files on an NMR server on the local network.	951912-951894-102074887
No access	951912-951894-102079790
nmr spectra are run by the nmr team	951912-951894-102133983
Individual accounts managed by the technician of the NMR	951912-951894-102162958
Each team has their own account and can access their data files but not another team's data files. The members of said team can access each	951912-951894-102176888

another team's data files. The members of said team can access each other's data files.

19 Are different levels of spectrometer access provided for users with different levels of expertise?

20 Which of the following describe categories of users in your facility? (select all that apply)

20.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 7 responses	
Non-expert users discuss experiments and science with the facility manager, who then decides on the experiments to run.	951912-951894-101360820
users who do not do the NMR experiments. These experiments are done by the core facility staff.	951912-951894-101693660
The facility provides support to research in different fields and industry however this experiments are carried out by the NMR technician or an expert user.	951912-951894-101690708
In reality, it's not the list of experiments available to users that describes their category of expertise, rather the amount of supervision provided/required. Non-expert users will naturally require full supervision, until they have proved and developed their abilities at the spectrometer.	951912-951894-101849988
supervised users - access with direct supervision only service users - spectra acquired by facility staff	951912-951894-101891636
Solution state: all users have access to "Edit all acquisition parameters..." option in IconNMR, but in practice no-one uses it, and the only thing routinely changed by users is the number of scans within IconNMR. Solid state: no guardrails!	951912-951894-102051473
the nmr team consists of expert users	951912-951894-102133983

21 If your facility has different categories of users, how is user expertise level assessed? (Please specify)

Showing all 95 responses	
Experts come from within the solid-state NMR research group. Everyone else is a non-expert in the technique but probably knows roughly what their materials are and what questions they want answered.	951912-951894-101360820
judgement of the users themselves	951912-951894-101369358
Users are assumed to be on the lowest level until appropriate training has been received.	951912-951894-101376470
Structured training levels	951912-951894-101376176
No assessment, "standard users" get a training	951912-951894-101397329
We have specialist users, who are able to run their own experiments in TopSpin without the support of NMR staff. These users must: i) Convince NMR staff that they will be regular users of our NMR instrumentation; ii) Be running experiments that are not normally available on open-access instrumentation; and iii) Once trained/during training display a sufficient level of competence to run and NMR experiment with the assistance of NMR staff.	951912-951894-101397499
most users are standard users. Only a couple of main users here are	951912-951894-101411307

most users are standard users. Only a couple of main users here are expert users - no specific assessment is done, but user experience and time on machine are considered.	951912-951894-101411307
By the facility manager	951912-951894-101421520
Users ability is assessed on a case-by-case basis	951912-951894-101445018
dedicated NMR personal is assessing expertise level, by evaluating ability to setup experiments (level 1 - basic) or write/modify pulse sequence (level 2- advanced).	951912-951894-101521141
By the user during project deposition (for national and transnational access). All local users are considered as experts.	951912-951894-101524313
By the staff	951912-951894-101550127
-preset experiment on automats with limited paramters accessibels - preset experiment on manual spectrometers with all the power set - solid state specialist in the facility - letting them do until they ask question	951912-951894-101559699
training and evaluation	951912-951894-101560777
Non expert : auto evaluation of the user and the falcility manager Standard : auto evaluation of the user and the falcility manager Expert: known in the NMR community and by the facility manager	951912-951894-101564816
Through dialogue	951912-951894-101577839
Personal training	951912-951894-101601534
By consultation. Most users are locally trained so expertise is well understood.	951912-951894-101603924
trained and licensed by NMR staff	951912-951894-101605905
It's going to depend on background of people. For exemple chemist or biologist will be trained on specific sequences but will be able to set up important parameters such as P1, O1 etc.... : this kind of users will be Classic à users. Then if the thematic of research of à group is around NMR spectroscopy and will need pur devices they will be considered as Expert Users for sure. To evaluate that there is discussion before access	951912-951894-101612738
Via internal training programs offered by the facility staff (2 x PhD level, 1 x MSc)	951912-951894-101613960
By default, everyone is "non expert". If an user needs wider access, the authorization is given by the facility manager after an assessment of the user's skills.	951912-951894-101613468
As approved by the platform manager	951912-951894-101618248
measuring first with expert user	951912-951894-101618364
Training and tests before facility used.	951912-951894-101613339
Standard users	951912-951894-101618407
evaluated and trained by a platform engineer.	951912-951894-101617105

Evaluation of skills after discussion	951912-951894-101635847
NMR labs are open to all users after training (by the NMR facility staff or by an experienced and certified user) and each user requires authorization by the NMR facility staff	
After evaluation by the operating manager, users are classified according to their NMR level which can be updated.	951912-951894-101614904
N/A	951912-951894-101642396
Training by NMR engineers for each level	951912-951894-101644803
Level 1 training for sample changers use Level 2 training for manual use	951912-951894-101648927
personal knowledge of the users	951912-951894-101663975
Initially people work under supervision and then gradually start to work independently.	951912-951894-101664309
Initially by following capacity and interest after training, and later on by assessing results and publication performance	951912-951894-101675332
3 different authorization types given by NMR facility staff	951912-951894-101683781
Formation and expertise evaluation are done by the core facility staff	951912-951894-101693660
Users with less experience are asked to be especially careful when conducting experiments with which they are not familiar.	951912-951894-101708184
User level is usually easy to assess during initial introduction and/or user training.	951912-951894-101709365
after a training one can become a standard user senior users with more than 10 years of expertise are the expert users	951912-951894-101713028
The manager of the facility selects between expert and non-expert users, based on a practical test, on the experience in NMR, and the needs of their research.	951912-951894-101728276
New students are chaperoned and trained by those more senior (2nd, 3rd, 4th year PhD students, Post-Docs, occasionally Profs). Visitors are assessed directly by the managers with their comfort level and generally make it known how much help they need.	951912-951894-101737673
We run most of the experiments for our users as most of them are users without NMR knowledge.	951912-951894-101741397
several short courses, lectures and training are provided	951912-951894-101742975
By preliminary discussion	951912-951894-101745973
Expert users: 10 ECTS practical NMR course, or equivalent knowledge Standard users: 0.5 day workshop + practical experience Non-expert users: 1 hour training + demo	951912-951894-101745527
Standard users must have in-house advanced training. This category represents most of the users in this facility.	951912-951894-101690708

Expert users are a limited number of people who have already gained hands-on experience and had higher training (e.g. EMBO, Jaca NMR School, Portuguese national NMR network workshops).	
Students are students PhD and post docs are considered standard users There are 1-3 senior users (experts)	951912-951894-101758405
There are operator training courses, level I. and II. At the end of the course the participant must pass the exam. For students this means a credit as well.	951912-951894-101647177
Through an evaluation (after training) by the facility staff	951912-951894-101768538
Personal knowledge, preliminary interviews and hands-on practice with senior researchers	951912-951894-101783128
Through theoretical and practical tests	951912-951894-101801357
By regular discussion about their need and the problems they face	951912-951894-101807038
Based on the training given locally	951912-951894-101830371
Expertise level is assessed through academic supervision	951912-951894-101834048
All new local users are required to attend a 'probes protection' course and pass written and 'driving' tests, after shadowing an experienced and accredited member of their group for a sufficient period of time. Only when staff are satisfied that they have reached the required ability are they provided with an individual account and login. Until then, they must rely on the support of an accredited user or member of facility staff. Responsibility for safe use of the NMR equipment is in the hands of the person logged in during a booking period, and not the person operating the spectrometer (if they are not the same person). New external users are supervised by facility staff initially to determine their ability at the spectrometer (in effect, a 'driving' test is conducted). Less confident/able users are given full supervision/training to allow them to become confident hands-on users. The facility access form completed by all hands-on users provides an initial indication of expertise, in which level of (perceived) expertise is requested.	951912-951894-101849988
training courses on 2 levels	951912-951894-101818532
Basic training allows access to limited experiment list on IconNMR, experience of NMR use and check with facility staff on requirements to access standard list on IconNMR, assessment and instruction by academic lead to run on TopSpin.	951912-951894-101889996
Background, project they are working on. Normally all our end users start as non-expert users and with the time and depending on their groups and projects, some of them they learn enough to become standard users	951912-951894-101890829
each users access is appraised based on: i) amount of NMR they require ii) amount of time they can dedicate to training for independent access iii) costs they can accommodate	951912-951894-101891636

<p>iii) costs they can accommodate</p> <p>Independent Standard users (can select from a wider list of experiments but cannot run their own pulse sequences) must: 1) undergo on-site training (as many hours as is required) 2) submit a protocol for NMR setup covering any and all experiments they want to run independently 3) sit a driving test with facility staff to check they are competent before sign-off</p>	
<p>Staff of the department is considered "expert users" and can do any experiment. A small selected group of persons from other departments is considered "non-expert users" and can do experiments exclusively in automation mode (sample changer). All other users do not have access to the spectrometers and must submit samples for measurements.</p>	951912-951894-101908122
<p>everyone passes standard NMR training. NMR lab members are considered expert users</p>	951912-951894-101956839
<p>With a test or exam</p>	951912-951894-101958432
<p>By personal training/interaction</p>	951912-951894-101836390
<p>All users are supervised by the platform engineers in the first period.</p>	951912-951894-101957336
<p>based on their knowledge of using the spectrometer</p>	951912-951894-101953004
<p>Scope of instruction and experience, task</p>	951912-951894-101968664
<p>They are supervised by the facility manager or an experienced postdoc until they can setup experiments without intervention from the supervisor</p>	951912-951894-101966822
<p>It is assessed from talking to each user.</p>	951912-951894-101902953
<p>short interview with facility staff</p>	951912-951894-102043034
<p>Users wanting an expert access to the non routine spectrometer is evaluated by me directly : discussion, training and checking on site. Such users are very few</p>	951912-951894-102045678
<p>Users are guided by local users or expert users. The number of experiments they do is mostly limited and can be repeated relatively easily once knowing the parameters to take care of. If the experiments get more challenging the expert user takes over. In many cases, the user wants to address a question using NMR and doesn't mind the experiments to be performed by local users or experts.</p>	951912-951894-102075878
<p>The categories of users will differ by group of users and their needs. Expertise is assessed during training</p>	951912-951894-102074887
<p>Only NMR researchers (including PhD students) are able to operate the spectrometers. Other users send the sample and the technician acquires the data.</p>	951912-951894-102079790
<p>Expert users are usually PhD students or postdocs doing NMR research.</p>	951912-951894-102094099
<p>Practical training and evaluation</p>	951912-951894-102107485

Standard users are trained by the expert users	951912-951894-102116982
Users have to undergo a training before they can access any NMR spectrometer. Depending on the level of NMR needed for their research access level will be discussed individually.	951912-951894-102121962
Non-expert users are undergraduate students who listened to a lecture about spectra acquisition and showed in practice knowledge of operations (sample insertion, manual tuning/matching), commands and experiments suitable to their needs. Access is granted to manual operation of 300 MHz and IconNMR operation on 500 MHz machines. Typical available experiment set is: 1H, 13C (cpd or apt), COSY, HSQC, HMBC Standard users have several years of experience and have a broader scope of available experiments. Expert user = facility manager	951912-951894-102129042
We have chemists for routine synthesis QC and we teach them how to use the 500 MHz spectrometer. On the 600/800 MHz we run biological NMR experiments for our users and some experts can use them autonomously. We judge their expertise from their background and accompanying them in their initial experiments. We also teach on-hands on the long-run PhD and postdocs (> 1 year NMR usage) to progressively become independent	951912-951894-102129825
The users are asked about their NMR background before they are allowed to access the spectrometers. They are often asked NMR and experimental setup by the permanent staff, to judge their level of expertise. Students are trained before they can access the spectrometers. They are asked to set up regular experiments on standard samples, before they can use it for other complicated samples.	951912-951894-102129570
The users get training at different levels depending on their research purposes when being introduced to the facility by the facility manager. The facility manager discusses first with the users' inquiries and decides the level of the training.	951912-951894-102130642
-	951912-951894-102131754
After a formation and according to their needs	951912-951894-102138055
according to research group	951912-951894-102149927
By a validation after training	951912-951894-102118767
All the users have to be trained before they can access the spectrometer. If they are not seriously trained, they cannot use the spectrometer.	951912-951894-102156909
MSc and PhD students Junior and Senior Researchers in Organic Chemistry	951912-951894-102162958
By level of training and experience	951912-951894-102166790
User expertise level is assessed according to their research activity. For instance, chemists are non-expert users, etc.	951912-951894-102165276
Via training and practice exams for each level.	951912-951894-102176888
i) Routine analysis users ii) NMR experts	951912-951894-102194221

Users get their approval after a training course	951912-951894-102223422
Only locally trained users are granted the the status of expert users. All others have standard user status.	951912-951894-102111780
Based on the history of user in the facility, experience on NMR usage in their host organization-	951912-951894-102291084

22 How is user NMR data kept secure and how do users access their data? (Please specify).

Showing all 114 responses	
No particular security although industrial data is removed from the spectrometer PCs' hard drives and stored on a separate machine. Non-expert users can only access their data via email link.	951912-951894-101360820
ftp access to spectrometers daily backup	951912-951894-101369358
Each research group has its own login, data gets copied via ICON-NMR to their data directories. Linux access right only for this group and the facility manager. Users login to the data server via scp file client.	951912-951894-101369602
Each user is owner of her/his data and solely responsible for safekeeping their data. Data access is by some FTP program or USB stick.	951912-951894-101370884
All data is copied onto a local server, which acts both as a backup and a method of access for local users. Access to data for less local users is still done on a more ad-hoc basis (email/teamviewer/FTP etc.) as appropriate for the user and data in question.	951912-951894-101372382
Copied to archive server (after acquisition). Read only access to data shares.	951912-951894-101376176
stored in multiple storage Data is transferred to the server space of the different workgroups	951912-951894-101397329
all data are backed up. access is through data server or directly from the spectrometer computer	951912-951894-101411307
University managed file system	951912-951894-101421520
Encrypted Hard drives with password protection. Data is accessed based on login credentials.	951912-951894-101445018
Password, vpn	951912-951894-101509032
double back up with one off-side, data on the machine cannot be deleted or overwritten. access via variety of remote access capabilities, varying over time and user.	951912-951894-101521141
Access is only possible through the local network infrastructure. For external users, data are usually transferred through cloud storage by the local operator.	951912-951894-101524313

Stored on internal HD with limited outside access. Access via OneDrive or USB. Alternatively, mailed by staff via email or filesender	951912-951894-101550127
via the LDAP of the school to connect on our server where the NMR data are stored	951912-951894-101559699
spectrometer data is transferred to a secured server.	951912-951894-101560777
Back up on local server in the lab every week	951912-951894-101564816
Server backups Most users get data via e-mail	951912-951894-101577839
backup to university data storage servers. Access via ssh.	951912-951894-101601534
No special security above Unix permissions. Data backed up nightly. Data transfers by SSH or file drop website.	951912-951894-101603924
Data is uploaded from spectrometers to a networked data server that can be accessed by users. Data is transferred to individual's data directory based on their staff/student/user ID.	951912-951894-101605905
We have a DMP on the platform and data are saved on several server on local and on national data center. Users have access thanks to FTP system	951912-951894-101612738
pushed (rsync) to a read only data server	951912-951894-101613960
each users data is stored in a specific directory with read/write access only for the user account (using linux file permissions). They can access their data remotely using sftp software	951912-951894-101613468
The spectrometer is accessible through ssh, sftp and vnc (protected with passwords). Data are saved using rsync on external drives	951912-951894-101614329
copy of the data are kept on a server 1. Users access to this server 1 to download their data on their own computer. Each six months, all the data are saved in another server 2 (no access for users) and the data on server 1 are deleted	951912-951894-101613305
The few external users do only get access to the spectrometer and data after extensive introduction and briefing. Typically the facility staff measures the data for external users and deposits the data.	951912-951894-101614161
Account by teams. Data access free in own institution and by vpn for all people.	951912-951894-101613339
Data is secured in a mesocentre. Users recover their data by a USB key...	951912-951894-101618407
by specific nmr server	951912-951894-101617105
Only registered users are allowed access to the spectrometers. Remote access requires VPN account. Data is accessed either via USB or via sftp/ssh. For external users data is sometimes sent via a secure data transfer system operated by the university.	951912-951894-101359111
Data are automatically uploaded on an archiving system (LOGS) and user can login and fetch their data from the server	951912-951894-101621258

Data will be stored on the NMR computer local hard disks and an automatic back-up will be performed every night on the lab server.	951912-951894-101635847
SSH File Transfer Protocol	
NMR computers are not accessible outside the local network of the institute (except with VPN access)	
login with remote access to copy (not modify) their own data.	951912-951894-101614904
Individual accounts, data transfer through remote login, no mounted disks.	951912-951894-101640129
NMR data can only be accessed via a connection to a server and after authentication of the access on a local network.	951912-951894-101644803
data directories are synced on a server that makes datasets available to users according to the dataset name. backup on a second server + manual backups of spectrometers on hard disks when supressing data	951912-951894-101648927
shared folder	951912-951894-101663975
We run a backup to a local server. Users access their data via LOGS (https://www.logs-repository.com/)	951912-951894-101664309
Each user was so far responsible for his/her own data. A back up copy was kept by the facility, for emergencies only. More recently we follow protocols of FAIR.	951912-951894-101675332
users get their spectra on a network drive and can only see their research group's results. For industry data are stored on a different disk, and are accessed only by the NMR facility staff. We send data manually or automatically by e-mail	951912-951894-101683781
The staff send the data to the users. Only users with permission are allowed to load their own date via Filezilla Security is performed by informatic service of University	951912-951894-101693660
Password-protected account (one for all users and one for the Administrator).	951912-951894-101700547
User NMR data is kept on a web server where each user group (project or lab, etc.) has its own account that only allows access to its data.	951912-951894-101708184
All data automatically backed up to a dedicated server in physically different location. Users have no access to other users data on Bruker installations (common account for everyone on Agilent). User access depends on the user: internal users can access data on the server (username and password protected); some external users have automated rsync to their own server over a secure connection. One time or rare users use ad hoc methods to access data.	951912-951894-101709365
The operating system of each spectrometer allows to access only own data. Data can only be removed either by the user or the administrator.	951912-951894-101725463
The data are saved on the workstations and on a backup server.	951912-951894-101728276

<p>The data are saved on the workstations and on a backup server.</p> <p>Users access their data by transferring them to the google drive of the university.</p>	
<p>The NMR data is sent automatically from the spectrometer to a NMR data server by clicking on an icon in the spectrometer control software (which runs a macro).</p> <p>The access to the data in the NMR server server is private for each user previous login and password (user has no access to other people's data). This server is accessible from internet.</p> <p>For better privacy the user optionally can delete his own data from the spectrometer PC once it has been sent to the NMR data server.</p>	951912-951894-101728393
<p>Industrial Users have an isolated file tree that is not accessible to anyone but the Local Managers and the Industrial users. This data is deleted upon request, or after a set amount of time. "Normal" users have access to their data through TeamViewer file transfer, through a user account provided by the university IT services, or through email file drop. Users are held to the honor system to only access their own data.</p>	951912-951894-101737673
<p>As we run most of the experiments for our users we keep the data separate and secure.</p>	951912-951894-101741397
<p>username/passwd sftp for file access to NAS USB sticks allowed (it's linux)</p>	951912-951894-101742975
<p>Data are backed up to two remote locations.</p> <p>User's own data are available for download from a file server</p>	951912-951894-101745973
<p>Data is synchronized to a central server every 30 minutes. All NMR-users have read-access to the server and all users' data. The server requires VPN access.</p> <p>For sensitive data, the data is stored in a folder without server-synchronization. After acquisition the data can be password protected and copied to server for retrieval.</p>	951912-951894-101745527
<p>Nmr data are stored on Nas drive</p>	951912-951894-101752958
<p>The users access the data, directly from the spectrometer, which is protected by an individual login or by FTP with a limited number of persons that can access. The users that have permission for external data access must be vetoed by the facility coordinator and it is administered by the IT of the university.</p>	951912-951894-101690708
<p>The is only one way exportation of data, from the spectrometer toward the data of users, and this is done undersupervision of experts.</p>	951912-951894-101758405
<p>There is a firewall, but internal users may access their own data.</p>	951912-951894-101647177
<p>Data is kept secure through periodic backup on university server Users access their data through WINScp (internal users) ; or data is sent</p>	951912-951894-101768538

Users access their data through WINSEP (internal users) , or data is sent through the university cloud (external users) by the facility staff.	
Data are saved in a server with restricted access	951912-951894-101783128
Users can only access their data through an internal web application. Users get access to only their data with three exclusive identification parameters. NMR Facility makes daily backups and verifies data integrity	951912-951894-101801357
All data are save onto two remote data servers	951912-951894-101807038
Data is transferred automatically to a safe shared drive supported by the local IT department. Access to the drive is granted by us. For other users, we transfer the data by online transfer services.	951912-951894-101809763
Stored locally on acquisition computers, new data copied to server every 20. minutes. The further copied to another server once a week	951912-951894-101830371
Data are stored on external disks and other workstations for processing) distributed through wetransfer or other file exchange applications. Users do not have access to the PC directly linked to the spectrometer	951912-951894-101834048
Data are stored on the facility firewall-protected data server, which sits behind the University firewall. While visiting the facility, users can access the data server via available workstations (PC and spectrometer-based) which are linked by the facility local subnet. Remote access to the data server and spectrometers (via the data server) is possible by ssh, for remote transfer of data.	951912-951894-101849988
personal login and password	951912-951894-101818532
Spectrometer PCs manually backed up approx. monthly to secure cloud storage. User access to data typically by exporting from spectrometer PC to external removable media	951912-951894-101889996
Data are stored locally in the NMR magnet PC and copied on a backup shared drive where end users can access. In principle all the folders are accessible by all end users with an account. We are trying to restrict that with our IT team so it is a "read only" mode.	951912-951894-101890829
All data acquired under automation are stored by our NOMAD system (https://www.nomad-nmr.uk/). Current version of NOMAD does not handle data acquired manually yet. We use spectrometers in manual mode only very occasionally and therefore need for development of that part of system is not that big. However, the feature is definitely on the road map.	951912-951894-101890690
Transfer to users home directory (with daily backup). Only users have access to their home directory.	951912-951894-101897907
data on central storage drive with backup and archive, access via windows explorer -> network drive	951912-951894-101903382
Access to spectrometer logins (and physical access to spectrometer PCs) is restricted - once access is granted all data on that spectrometer is open (see below). The facility keeps confidentiality mainly by anonymity of	951912-951894-101891636

<p>/ can be viewed. The facility keeps confidentiality mainly by anonymity or the dataset name / details (rather than permission structure) but this is something we wish to review.</p> <p>Linux allows for periodic backups (direct to specific users password protected accounts) and removal of sensitive data from the spectrometer PC in a timely manner.</p> <p>Approved users can access data on the spectrometer direct from linux using secure shell (ssh) or facility staff will send datasets to external users via wetransfer.com</p>	
Data are provided "read only" for all users, they are copied from the spectrometer data stations to a separate server for this purpose. No distinction is made regarding the origin or "owner" of the data.	951912-951894-101908122
The PC controlling the spectrometer are kept behind the institute's firewall; users can transfer their data to their local datastations (within the institute) using secured protocols approved by our IT, but all within the institute's firewall.	951912-951894-101518991
With a internal server with a security copy.	951912-951894-101958432
by a password on the PC, access via sftp or ssh	951912-951894-101836390
Spectrometer data are backed up every night	951912-951894-101957336
external (mostly industrial) users data are kept in password protected folders	951912-951894-101953004
see above, server backup daily, access via remote desktop, intranet	951912-951894-101968664
Users copy data onto their own university accounts for further analysis and are themselves responsible for keeping it secure and backed up.	951912-951894-101966822
Part of the data is protected by GDPR and secured with two-factor login for authorised personnel only.	951912-951894-101902953
Other data is located in-house and secured by fire walls.	
User data is uploaded (e.g. on OneDrive or sent by email). In-house users may fetch data with ssh.	
data is stored on a secure server. users have read only access. data is segregated into research group mount points.	951912-951894-102043034
Data are stored in a onsite server. Data are available per group through a restricted accessed website (access from the Campus or through the University VPN). Login is managed with the same tools than the University websites (same shibboleth checking access)	951912-951894-102045678
Solution state: automated archiving to university fileserver, access to which requires authentication using university credentials (VPN if off-campus). Physical access to NMR lab controlled using university ID cards, and USB drives disabled for Windows machines.	951912-951894-102051473
Solids: physical access to NMR lab controlled using university ID cards, ad hoc arrangements with USB drives	
They can download data from SFTP or on a server	951912-951894-102074778

lokale user data can be accessed by others and accessed using scftp/wetransfer. If needed, data will be send to external users and can be deleted upon request. Expert users use passwords to disable others access.	951912-951894-102075878
Data is located on a shared network drive	951912-951894-102078028
Data located on a server is accessible by local users only.	951912-951894-102074887
External users data is shared via a private shared drive or sent privately via email	
Sent by email.	951912-951894-102079790
Hard-drive with a cloud copy.	951912-951894-102086754
Users access data through password protected shared folders via the university LAN.	951912-951894-102094099
Login/PW for each user.	951912-951894-102107485
Data secured by passwd. Access of the data through intranet.	951912-951894-102109484
Data access is protected by passwords	951912-951894-102116982
The platform manager send the data personally to the user after the experiments have been performed. Data are backed up on an external disk system	951912-951894-102093469
Data is backed up into an external server. Users access this external server and not the spectrometer computer when they want to access the data.	951912-951894-102119682
Data is saved on a data server which only can be accesed by username and password. Access is only possible within the institution	951912-951894-102121962
Data is synchronized to a dedicated server that is acceptable from department workstations. Data of external users/clients are sent by email. Only some of standard users and expert user have access to data on an NMR workstation. Remote access to the workstations is available only to the manager and local IT support.	951912-951894-102129042
Data are saved on the spectrometers PCs and automatically copied to institutional servers that backup data. Chemists have a dedicated space shared by a laboratory where they can access their data and copy it to their machines. Biological NMR experts access and analyse their data on institutional servers with dedicated NMR software that we mantain	951912-951894-102129825
We have a script to upload every day's new NMR data to the university share drive during midnight, which is managed by the facility. We can give users access to the drive. The users have read-only right in the share drive, but they can transfer the data to their computer to work on.	951912-951894-102130642
Storage of all files in another computer. Spectra are sent by email.	951912-951894-102131754
They access the data by AnyDesk software.	951912-951894-102134862
Using LOGS repository solution	951912-951894-102136549

nmr spectra are located on a specific nmr server (linux) working as a samba server. Each local user can access the data with a specific password. Access will be granted on basis of ip addresses.	951912-951894-102133983
data are saved on an university server and on a specific directory for each user	951912-951894-102138055
For local users : Data is written directly to a shared drive with user authentication. For external users : A secure download link is sent by the platform manager by mail.	951912-951894-102118767
NMR data kept secure on a local hard disk and a server. Internal user access their data via a ssh login. External user can copy they data on a disk under the control of their internal collaborator.	951912-951894-102156909
Users access their spectra by email sent by the technician, and they are kept in the computer and in an external disk (backups)	951912-951894-102162958
User access is restricted to internal networks. Users can access through the network or donwload data to pendrives	951912-951894-102166790
Individual account with spectific login and password --> indivual NMR data Access to user NMR data by securised FTP protocol	951912-951894-102165276
Different password-protected user accounts in Windows operation system and TopSpin/IconNMR programs. Local users have both local (onsite computer) and remote access (must have specific program and password). Industrial users have their own user account but their data are send to them - they don't have any direct access to the infrastructure.	951912-951894-102176888
distant servers	951912-951894-102191184
Each user makes its own backup of the data and keep it in personal computers	951912-951894-102243367
Data is given to user using the secure file sender system, or on a physical device. The data is behind the firewall system and regular backups are made.	951912-951894-102291084

- 23** Prior to, during and since the Covid19 pandemic, did you provide remote access to one or more of the NMR spectrometers in your facility? By remote access, we mean that either: 1) users could directly operate the NMR spectrometer by remote login to the NMR spectrometer computer (direct remote access), or 2) users could communicate via a computer linkup (Zoom/Teams etc) or telephone with a local operator who controlled the NMR spectrometer based on the information provided by the remote user (assisted remote access), or 3) some other type of remote access.

23.a If you would like to provide more detailed information about your mode of remote spectrometer access then please fill in the text box.

Showing first 5 of 59 responses	
Initially allowed expert users to use TeamViewer but now use DWService. Non-expert users have no remote access (and don't need it) because the facility manager runs experiments for them.	951912-951894-101360820
teamviewer access but not generally allowed, only for selected users	951912-951894-101369358
Staff and selected users have credentials to access the spectrometers via VNC.	951912-951894-101376470
Bruker IconWeb	951912-951894-101376176
Over Iconnmr Webinterface	951912-951894-101397329

23.b Why has remote access to spectrometers not been implemented in your facility? (select any that apply)

23.b.i If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 9 responses	
No professional IT resources to implement it.	951912-951894-101524313
We don't have ATMA (automatic tune and match), which is common in solid-state NMR. Nevertheless for samples in which experiments run for several days, it would be nice to change experimental parameters and start new experiments from anywhere.	951912-951894-101664309
Currently the users that require hands-on on the spectrometer are all of them local (university). External users what they do up to now is to sent the samples to the NMR lab and we provide the NMR measurements for them.	951912-951894-101728393
The lack of expertise of our end users made it impossible. We cannot trust them. They just know how to operate the instrument in automatic mode. Past experiences taught us they cannot have admin rights or autonomy to operate the magnet themselves for troubleshooting or anything outside the standard experiments in IconNMR. Also, there is a high turnover of students every year, so there is a small number of people who becomes confident to use the instrument. If anything, we would implement remote access for a selected group of people with different levels of access.	951912-951894-101890829
no ATMA probes, sample preparation challenges	951912-951894-101894250
In our experience running topspin remote needs very fast and broad internet resources which we do not always have	951912-951894-101968664
During the first lockdown, all labs were closed. With the following lockdown, a booking website was implemented allowing access to the lab, but for onsite users one per one. Sanitary measures were implemented (one user at a time ; use of hydro alcoholic gel)	951912-951894-102045678
Only NMR staff had access to the spectrometers and were running all the samples of users	951912-951894-102074887
The research process, which is the major source of the users/samples, has not stopped and onsite access was available with all safety precautions. Remote access would only be needed if no one would be able to come to work, but then there would be no samples to analyze.	951912-951894-102129042

23.c The aim of the Remote-NMR project is to develop a common framework for remote spectrometer access taking into account best practice across the EU/UK. Standardized training for remote access will also be put in place. Once this has been completed, would your NMR facility be interested in implementing remote spectrometer access?

APPENDIX 3

Remote-NMR (R-NMR): Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities

NMR FACILITY MANAGER SURVEY (2-24 November 2022)

Univ. of Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee Approval Reference: [R77838/RE001]

SUMMARY OF RESPONSES FROM NMR FACILITIES PROVIDING REMOTE ACCESS

Introduction

Lockdown restrictions in many countries during 2020-2021 Covid19 pandemic resulted in the implementation of remote access to NMR spectrometers as a way of enabling the continuation of important research. The experiences of several European NMR facilities during the pandemic have shown that this access mode can work well within the field of NMR spectroscopy. It is the aim of the Remote-NMR project to develop and exploit remote access to NMR facilities. Work Package 2 within R-NMR focusses on the “Remote NMR Landscape”. Task 2.1 within WP2 is a review of current protocols in place for remote access to NMR facilities, including statistics on current implementation of remote access. This information has been collected via an online survey of NMR facility managers.

This document is a summary of the subset of responses from 83 NMR facility managers at facilities that did provide remote access to their NMR spectrometers.

Questions 27-30 asked about the distribution of remote access users between: Local users, National users, Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide, Industrial users. The breakdown of users was as follows.

27 - Local users:

0 0.0%
1-10 65.7%
11-20 18.6%
>20 15.7%

28 – National users:

0 45.5%
1-10 52.3%
11-20 0.0%
>20 2.3%

29 – Transnational users:

0 73.7%
1-10 23.7%
11-20 2.6%

30 – Industrial users:

0 78.6%
1-10 21.4%

Remote-NMR: NMR Facility Manager Survey

Showing 83 of 142 responses

Showing **all** responses

Hiding question **44**

With filter **q23-is-yes-direct-remote-access-or-yes-assisted-remote-access-or-yes-both-direct-and-assisted-remote-access-or-yes-another-type-of-remote-access-please-specify-below** applied

- 1** You are invited to complete this online survey aimed at NMR facility managers. We will ask questions about your NMR facility, your experiences with providing remote access to NMR spectrometers and for your views on how remote access can be improved in the future. The survey can be completed without providing your name or contact email address but you will be asked to indicate in which country your NMR facility is located. There will be the option to provide more detailed information via a one-to-one online interview; in this case you will be asked to provide your name/email address so that you can be contacted directly. Information that you provide about your experiences with remote access will be included in discussions with other R-NMR project participants and in project reports; however this information will not be associated with your name or your email address. All survey data will be stored at the University of Oxford on a secure computer (password protected and behind a firewall) during the duration of the R-NMR project (until 30 June 2025). An anonymised version of the survey (without any name/email information) will be created for longer-term storage. We intend to keep this version for 3 years after publication of the outcome of the project. Please confirm below: That you have read this information, and if you require further detailed information, that you have read the Participant Information Sheet. That you understand who will have access to any personal data that you provide, how data will be stored and what will happen to data at the end of the project. That you understand how to raise a concern or make a complaint. That you are willing to continue with the survey.

Yes 83 (100%)
No | 0

- 2** Please confirm that you are the manager of an NMR facility. (Please try to ensure that the survey is only completed by one person involved in the management of your NMR facility).

Yes 83 (100%)
No | 0

- 3** In which country is your NMR facility located? Select one:

3.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing 1 response	
Australia	951912-951894-101605905

4 Is your NMR facility part of a national infrastructure?

5 How many spectrometers do you have in your NMR facility?

6 At what 1H frequencies do your spectrometers operate? (select all that apply)

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

7 What type of spectrometers do you have in your facility? (select all that apply)

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

7.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 7 responses	
Stelar FFC relaxometer 200MHz with RS2D console	951912-951894-101613468
Magritek	951912-951894-101644910
RS2D	951912-951894-101648927
Nanalysis benchtop	951912-951894-101745527
Magritek RS2D	951912-951894-101768538
Home build/developed fast field cycling relaxometer	951912-951894-102073777
Pure Devices	951912-951894-102130642

8 What data acquisition software do your spectrometers run? (select all that apply)

8.a If you selected Bruker TopSpin, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 78 responses	
3.6.2	951912-951894-101360820
3.5 4.1	951912-951894-101369358
4.1.1	951912-951894-101372382
3.6.5 3.6.4 3.2.7	951912-951894-101376470
2.1pl8 3.5pl7 3.6.2	951912-951894-101397329

8.b If you selected Bruker IconNMR, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 25 responses	
5.0.12 4.7.7	951912-951894-101376470
5.0.11 and 5.2.4	951912-951894-101445018
5.0.12 4.7.5	951912-951894-101577839
5.1.8 5.0.10	951912-951894-101605905
3.5	951912-951894-101613468

8.c If you selected Agilent Vnmrj, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing all 11 responses	
4.2	951912-951894-101644910
OpenVnmrj 2.1A	951912-951894-101675332
OpenVnmrj 3.1	951912-951894-101709365
Vnmrj 3.2	951912-951894-101713028
4.2	951912-951894-101818436
4	951912-951894-101795121
4	951912-951894-102043034
vnmrj 2.2.D vnmrj 4.2.A	951912-951894-102075878
OpenVNMJRJ 3.1A	951912-951894-102121962
vnmrj 4.2	951912-951894-102133983
Vnmrj 3.2	951912-951894-102149927

8.d If you selected JEOL Delta, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing all 2 responses	
5.3.1	951912-951894-101411307
5.2	951912-951894-101642396

8.e If you selected GE/Omega, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

No responses

8.f If you selected Other, please specify the software name and version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing all 8 responses	
RS2D Spinit Stelar FFC software	951912-951894-101613468
Magritek Spinsolve	951912-951894-101644910
SpinIt	951912-951894-101648927
SpinSight	951912-951894-101737673
Spinsolve Expert (Magritek) SpinIt (RS2D)	951912-951894-101768538
Bruker paravision 6	951912-951894-101783128
Home developed based on Matlab	951912-951894-102073777
Paravision360 v3.3	951912-951894-102130642

9 What operating systems do your spectrometer computers run? (select all that apply)

9.a If you selected Linux, please specify the distribution (Debian, Fedora etc) and version.

Showing first 5 of 52 responses	
CentOS	951912-951894-101369358
CentOS 7	951912-951894-101376470
CentOS 7.9	951912-951894-101376176
Centos 5.11	951912-951894-101411307
CentOS 7	951912-951894-101445018

9.b If you selected Windows, please specify the version.

Showing first 5 of 40 responses	
10	951912-951894-101360820
10	951912-951894-101372382
Win10 pro 21H1	951912-951894-101376176
XP Windows7 Windows9	951912-951894-101397329
windows 7	951912-951894-101411307

9.c If you selected Mac OS, please specify the version.

No responses

9.d If you selected Other, please specify the operating system and version.

Showing 1 response	
Sun Microsystems	951912-951894-101737673

10 What type of NMR are the spectrometers in your facility equipped for? (select one)

11 Tell us about the users of your NMR facility. (select all that apply)

12 What types of NMR experiments do your users carry out? (select all that apply)

12.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 12 responses	
Work that would fall under the NERC remit (soils, mineralogical samples, etc.).	951912-951894-101360820
De novo structure elucidation	951912-951894-101577839
polymer	951912-951894-101617105
Methodology development (hyperpolarization) and equipment development (probes)	951912-951894-101709365
Relaxometry, diffusometry	951912-951894-101783128
Metabolic tracing research	951912-951894-101849988
complex mixtures	951912-951894-101953004
Hyperpolarization experiments using pH2 and DNP	951912-951894-102075878
Natural Product chemistry Glycochemistry Fluorine compounds (19F-QCI 600MHz probe) 13C NMR (TXO probe, 700MHz) High pressure NMR (daedalus -> 3kbar)	951912-951894-102093469
soft matter analyses wit a HR MAS probe	951912-951894-102133983
pharmaceutical analysis	951912-951894-102138055
Natural Product chemistry (600MHz equipped with a microprobe) Glycochemistry	951912-951894-102118767

13 On average, how many users does your facility have in a year?

14 Local users

Showing first 5 of 78 responses	
5 PIs	951912-951894-101360820
50	951912-951894-101369358
30	951912-951894-101372382
200	951912-951894-101376470
<50	951912-951894-101376176

15 National users

Showing first 5 of 64 responses	
3 PIs	951912-951894-101360820
4	951912-951894-101369358
5	951912-951894-101372382
0	951912-951894-101376176
5	951912-951894-101397329

16 Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide)

Showing first 5 of 47 responses	
1-2 PIs	951912-951894-101360820
0	951912-951894-101372382
0	951912-951894-101376176
0	951912-951894-101397329
0	951912-951894-101509032

17 Industrial users

Showing first 5 of 66 responses	
0-1 Organisations	951912-951894-101360820
4	951912-951894-101369358
0	951912-951894-101372382
10	951912-951894-101376470
0	951912-951894-101376176

18 How do users of your NMR facility login to the spectrometers and do they have access to other users' data? (select all that apply)

18.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 16 responses	
Solid-state NMR research group users can access the shared login for running experiments and viewing data. Other users submit samples which are run by the facility manager, who then emails out a link to their data in a zip file on Dropbox.	951912-951894-101360820
Individual accounts with access to other users' files	951912-951894-101376176
Measurements are performed by the staff	951912-951894-101509032
Individual accounts with access to others files controlled by UNIX permissions	951912-951894-101603924
>Shared account amongst research group users- data not shared with other research groups >Open-access - no login required.	951912-951894-101605905
individual accounts and access to other users' files	951912-951894-101613305
Individual accounts with open access to other users' files within the same research group, read only access to other files.	951912-951894-101640129
Individual Accounts with access to other's files with an option for a sequestered environment if needed.	951912-951894-101737673
Individual accounts with limited access to other users' files	951912-951894-101745973
Individual accounts with possible access to other users' files depending on permissions set by account owners. Users can share data/files if they choose to. Account holders can belong to specific groups and decide who they share files with.	951912-951894-101849988
Individual accounts with limited access to other user's files	951912-951894-101518991
Individual accounts with access to other users' files in read only mode	951912-951894-101957336
For non-local users we only provide short-term login accounts.	951912-951894-101902953
Solution state: open access with shared Windows perma-login, but individual accounts in IconNMR. Users can see other users' files. Solids: individual Linux accounts, and users cannot access other users' files	951912-951894-102051473
nmr spectra are run by the nmr team	951912-951894-102133983
Each team has their own account and can access their data files but not another team's data files. The members of said team can access each other's data files.	951912-951894-102176888

19 Are different levels of spectrometer access provided for users with different levels of expertise?

20 Which of the following describe categories of users in your facility? (select all that apply)

20.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 6 responses	
Non-expert users discuss experiments and science with the facility manager, who then decides on the experiments to run.	951912-951894-101360820
users who do not do the NMR experiments. These experiments are done by the core facility staff.	951912-951894-101693660
In reality, it's not the list of experiments available to users that describes their category of expertise, rather the amount of supervision provided/required. Non-expert users will naturally require full supervision, until they have proved and developed their abilities at the spectrometer.	951912-951894-101849988
supervised users - access with direct supervision only service users - spectra acquired by facility staff	951912-951894-101891636
Solution state: all users have access to "Edit all acquisition parameters..." option in IconNMR, but in practice no-one uses it, and the only thing routinely changed by users is the number of scans within IconNMR. Solid state: no guardrails!	951912-951894-102051473
the nmr team consists of expert users	951912-951894-102133983

21 If your facility has different categories of users, how is user expertise level assessed? (Please specify)

Showing all 57 responses	
Experts come from within the solid-state NMR research group. Everyone else is a non-expert in the technique but probably knows roughly what their materials are and what questions they want answered.	951912-951894-101360820
judgement of the users themselves	951912-951894-101369358
Users are assumed to be on the lowest level until appropriate training has been received.	951912-951894-101376470
Structured training levels	951912-951894-101376176
No assessment, "standard users" get a training	951912-951894-101397329
most users are standard users. Only a couple of main users here are expert users - no specific assessment is done, but user experience and time on machine are considered.	951912-951894-101411307
By the facility manager	951912-951894-101421520
Users ability is assessed on a case-by-case basis	951912-951894-101445018
dedicated NMR personal is assessing expertise level, by evaluating ability to setup experiments (level 1 - basic) or write/modify pulse sequence (level 2- advanced).	951912-951894-101521141
Non expert : auto evaluation of the user and the facility manager	951912-951894-101564816

Standard : auto evaluation of the user and the facility manager Expert: known in the NMR community and by the facility manager	
Through dialogue	951912-951894-101577839
Personal training	951912-951894-101601534
By consultation. Most users are locally trained so expertise is well understood.	951912-951894-101603924
trained and licensed by NMR staff	951912-951894-101605905
It's going to depend on background of people. For example chemist or biologist will be trained on specific sequences but will be able to set up important parameters such as P1, O1 etc.... : this kind of users will be Classic à users. Then if the thematic of research of a group is around NMR spectroscopy and will need pur devices they will be considered as Expert Users for sure. To evaluate that there is discussion before access	951912-951894-101612738
By default, everyone is "non expert". If an user needs wider access, the authorization is given by the facility manager after an assessment of the user's skills.	951912-951894-101613468
measuring first with expert user	951912-951894-101618364
evaluated and trained by a platform engineer.	951912-951894-101617105
N/A	951912-951894-101642396
Level 1 training for sample changers use Level 2 training for manual use	951912-951894-101648927
Initially by following capacity and interest after training, and later on by assessing results and publication performance	951912-951894-101675332
3 different authorization types given by NMR facility staff	951912-951894-101683781
Formation and expertise evaluation are done by the core facility staff	951912-951894-101693660
Users with less experience are asked to be especially careful when conducting experiments with which they are not familiar.	951912-951894-101708184
User level is usually easy to assess during initial introduction and/or user training.	951912-951894-101709365
after a training one can become a standard user senior users with more than 10 years of expertise are the expert users	951912-951894-101713028
The manager of the facility selects between expert and non-expert users, based on a practical test, on the experience in nmr, and the needs of their research.	951912-951894-101728276
New students are chaperoned and trained by those more senior (2nd, 3rd, 4th year PhD students, Post-Docs, occasionally Profs). Visitors are assessed directly by the managers with their comfort level and generally make it known how much help they need.	951912-951894-101737673
We run most of the experiments for our users as most of them are users without NMR knowledge.	951912-951894-101741397

By preliminary discussion	951912-951894-101745973
Expert users: 10 ects practical NMR course, or equivalent knowledge Standard users: 0.5 day workshop + practical experience Non-expert users: 1 hour training + demo	951912-951894-101745527
There are operator training courses, level I. and II. At the end of the course the participant must pass the exam. For students this means a credit as well.	951912-951894-101647177
Through an evaluation (after training) by the facility staff	951912-951894-101768538
Personal knowledge, preliminary interviews and hands-on practice with senior researchers	951912-951894-101783128
By regular discussion about their need and the problems they face	951912-951894-101807038
Based on the training given locally	951912-951894-101830371
Expertise level is assessed through academic supervision	951912-951894-101834048
<p>All new local users are required to attend a 'probes protection' course and pass written and 'driving' tests, after shadowing an experienced and accredited member of their group for a sufficient period of time. Only when staff are satisfied that they have reached the required ability are they provided with an individual account and login. Until then, they must rely on the support of an accredited user or member of facility staff. Responsibility for safe use of the NMR equipment is in the hands of the person logged in during a booking period, and not the person operating the spectrometer (if they are not the same person).</p> <p>New external users are supervised by facility staff initially to determine their ability at the spectrometer (in effect, a 'driving' test is conducted). Less confident/able users are given full supervision/training to allow them to become confident hands-on users.</p> <p>The facility access form completed by all hands-on users provides an initial indication of expertise, in which level of (perceived) expertise is requested.</p>	951912-951894-101849988
<p>each users access is appraised based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) amount of NMR they require ii) amount of time they can dedicate to training for independent access iii) costs they can accommodate <p>Independent Standard users (can select from a wider list of experiments but cannot run their own pulse sequences) must: 1) undergo on-site training (as many hours as is required) 2) submit a protocol for NMR setup covering any and all experiments they want to run independently 3) sit a driving test with facility staff to check they are competent before sign-off</p>	951912-951894-101891636
With a test or exam	951912-951894-101958432
All users are supervised by the platform engineers in the first period.	951912-951894-101957336
based on their knowledge of using the spectrometer	951912-951894-101953004

They are supervised by the facility manager or an experienced postdoc until they can setup experiments without intervention from the supervisor	951912-951894-101966822
It is assessed from talking to each user.	951912-951894-101902953
short interview with facility staff	951912-951894-102043034
Users are guided by local users or expert users. The number of experiments they do is mostly limited and can be repeated relatively easily once knowing the parameters to take care of. If the experiments get more challenging the expert user takes over. In many cases, the user wants to address a question using NMR and doesn't mind the experiments to be performed by local users or experts.	951912-951894-102075878
Expert users are usually PhD students or postdocs doing NMR research.	951912-951894-102094099
Users have to undergo a training before they can access any NMR spectrometer. Depending on the level of NMR needed for their research access level will be discussed individually.	951912-951894-102121962
We have chemists for routine synthesis QC and we teach them how to use the 500 MHz spectrometer. On the 600/800 MHz we run biological NMR experiments for our users and some experts can use them autonomously. We judge their expertise from their background and accompanying them in their initial experiments. We also teach on-hands on the long-run PhD and postdocs (> 1 year NMR usage) to progressively become independent	951912-951894-102129825
The users get training at different levels depending on their research purposes when being introduced to the facility by the facility manager. The facility manager discusses first with the users' inquiries and decides the level of the training.	951912-951894-102130642
After a formation and according to their needs	951912-951894-102138055
according to research group	951912-951894-102149927
By a validation after training	951912-951894-102118767
All the users have to be trained before they can access the spectrometer. If they are not seriously trained, they cannot use the spectrometer.	951912-951894-102156909
User expertise level is assessed according to their research activity. For instance, chemists are non-expert users, etc.	951912-951894-102165276
Via training and practice exams for each level.	951912-951894-102176888
Based on the history of user in the facility, experience on NMR usage in their host organization-	951912-951894-102291084

22 How is user NMR data kept secure and how do users access their data? (Please specify).

Showing all 70 responses	
No particular security although industrial data is removed from the spectrometer PCs' hard drives and stored on a separate machine. Non-	951912-951894-101360820

expert users can only access their data via email link.	
ftp access to spectrometers daily backup	951912-951894-101369358
All data is copied onto a local server, which acts both as a backup and a method of access for local users. Access to data for less local users is still done on a more ad-hoc basis (email/teamviewer/FTP etc.) as appropriate for the user and data in question.	951912-951894-101372382
Copied to archive server (after acquisition). Read only access to data shares.	951912-951894-101376176
stored in multiple storage Data is transferred to the server space of the different workgroups	951912-951894-101397329
all data are backed up. access is through data server or directly from the spectrometer computer	951912-951894-101411307
University managed file system	951912-951894-101421520
Encrypted Hard drives with password protection. Data is accessed based on login credentials.	951912-951894-101445018
Password, vpn	951912-951894-101509032
double back up with one off-side, data on the machine cannot be deleted or overwritten. access via variety of remote access capabilities, varying over time and user.	951912-951894-101521141
Back up on local server in the lab every week	951912-951894-101564816
Server backups Most users get data via e-mail	951912-951894-101577839
backup to university data storage servers. Access via ssh.	951912-951894-101601534
No special security above Unix permissions. Data backed up nightly. Data transfers by SSH or file drop website.	951912-951894-101603924
Data is uploaded from spectrometers to a networked data server that can be accessed by users. Data is transferred to individual's data directory based on their staff/student/user ID.	951912-951894-101605905
We have a DMP on the platform and data are saved on several server un local and on national data center. Users have access thanks to FTP system	951912-951894-101612738
each users data is stored in a specific directory with read/write access only for the user account (using linux file permissions). They can access their data remotely using sftp software	951912-951894-101613468
The spectrometer is accessible through ssh, sftp and vnc (protected with passwords). Data are saved using rsync on external drives	951912-951894-101614329
copy of the data are kept on a server 1. Users acces to this server 1 to download their data on their own computer Each six month, all the data are save in an other server 2 (no access for users) and the data on server	951912-951894-101613305

1 are deleted	
by specific nmr server	951912-951894-101617105
Only registered users are allowed access to the spectrometers. Remote access requires VPN account. Data is accessed either via USB or via sftp/ssh. For external users data is sometimes sent via a secure data transfer system operated by the university.	951912-951894-101359111
Individual accounts, data transfer through remote login, no mounted disks.	951912-951894-101640129
data directories are synced on a server that makes datasets available to users according to the dataset name. backup on a second server + manual backups of spectrometers on hard disks when supressing data	951912-951894-101648927
Each user was so far responsible for his/her own data. A back up copy was kept by the facility, for emergencies only. More recently we follow protocols of FAIR.	951912-951894-101675332
users get their spectra on a network drive and can only see their research group's results. For industry data are stored on a different disk, and are accessed only by the NMR facility staff. We send data manually or automatically by e-mail	951912-951894-101683781
The staff send the data to the users. Only users with permission are allowed to load their own date via Filezilla Security is performed by informatic service of University	951912-951894-101693660
User NMR data is kept on a web server where each user group (project or lab, etc.) has its own account that only allows access to its data.	951912-951894-101708184
All data automatically backed up to a dedicated server in physically different location. Users have no access to other users data on Bruker installations (common account for everyone on Agilent). User access depends on the user: internal users can access data on the server (username and password protected); some external users have automated rsync to their own server over a secure connection. One time or rare users use ad hoc methods to access data.	951912-951894-101709365
The operating system of each spectrometer allows to access only own data. Data can only be removed either by the user or the administrator.	951912-951894-101725463
The data are saved on the workstations and on a backup server. Users access their data by transferring them to the google drive of the university.	951912-951894-101728276
Industrial Users have an isolated file tree that is not accessible to anyone but the Local Managers and the Industrial users. This data is deleted upon request, or after a set amount of time. "Normal" users have access to their data through TeamViewer file transfer, through a user account provided by the university IT services, or through email file drop. Users are held to the honor system to only access their own data.	951912-951894-101737673
As we run most of the experiments for our users we keep the data separate and secure.	951912-951894-101741397

Data are backed up to two remote locations. User's own data are available for download from a file server	951912-951894-101745973
Data is synchronized to a central server every 30 minutes. All NMR-users have read-access to the server and all users' data. The server requires VPN access. For sensitive data, the data is stored in a folder without server-synchronization. After acquisition the data can be password protected and copied to server for retrieval.	951912-951894-101745527
Nmr data are stored on Nas drive	951912-951894-101752958
There is a firewall, but internal users may access their own data.	951912-951894-101647177
Data is kept secure through periodic backup on university server Users access their data through WINScp (internal users) ; or data is sent through the university cloud (external users) by the facility staff.	951912-951894-101768538
Data are saved in a server with restricted access	951912-951894-101783128
All data are save onto two remote data servers	951912-951894-101807038
Stored locally on acquisition computers, new data copied to server every 20. minutes. The further copied to another server once a week	951912-951894-101830371
Data are stored on external disks and other workstations for processing) distributed through wetransfer or other file exchange applications. Users do not have access to the PC directly linked to the spectrometer	951912-951894-101834048
Data are stored on the facility firewall-protected data server, which sits behind the University firewall. While visiting the facility, users can access the data server via available workstations (PC and spectrometer-based) which are linked by the facility local subnet. Remote access to the data server and spectrometers (via the data server) is possible by ssh, for remote transfer of data.	951912-951894-101849988
Transfer to users home directory (with daily backup). Only users have access to their home directory.	951912-951894-101897907
data on central storage drive with backup and archive, access via windows explorer -> network drive	951912-951894-101903382
Access to spectrometer logins (and physical access to spectrometer PCs) is restricted - once access is granted all data on that spectrometer is open / can be viewed. The facility keeps confidentiality mainly by anonymity of the dataset name / details (rather than permission structure) but this is something we wish to review. Linux allows for periodic backups (direct to specific users password protected accounts) and removal of sensitive data from the spectrometer PC in a timely manner. Approved users can access data on the spectrometer direct from linux using secure shell (ssh) or facility staff will send datasets to external users	951912-951894-101891636

via wetransfer.com	
The PC controlling the spectrometer are kept behind the institute's firewall; users can transfer their data to their local datastations (within the institute) using secured protocols approved by our IT, but all within the institute's firewall.	951912-951894-101518991
With a internal server with a security copy.	951912-951894-101958432
Spectrometer data are backed up every night	951912-951894-101957336
external (mostly industrial) users data are kept in password protected folders	951912-951894-101953004
Users copy data onto their own university accounts for further analysis and are themselves responsible for keeping it secure and backed up.	951912-951894-101966822
Part of the data is protected by GDPR and secured with two-factor login for authorised personnel only. Other data is located in-house and secured by fire walls. User data is uploaded (e.g. on OneDrive or sent by email). In-house users may fetch data with ssh.	951912-951894-101902953
data is stored on a secure server. users have read only access. data is segregated into research group mount points.	951912-951894-102043034
Solution state: automated archiving to university fileserver, access to which requires authentication using university credentials (VPN if off-campus). Physical access to NMR lab controlled using university ID cards, and USB drives disabled for Windows machines. Solids: physical access to NMR lab controlled using university ID cards, ad hoc arrangements with USB drives	951912-951894-102051473
They can download data from SFTP or on a server	951912-951894-102074778
lokale user data can be accessed by others and accessed using scftp/wetransfer. If needed, data will be send to external users and can be deleted upon request. Expert users use passwords to disable others access.	951912-951894-102075878
Users access data through password protected shared folders via the university LAN.	951912-951894-102094099
The platform manager send the data personally to the user after the experiments have been performed. Data are backed up on an external disk system	951912-951894-102093469
Data is backed up into an external server. Users access this external server and not the spectrometer computer when they want to access the data.	951912-951894-102119682
Data is saved on a data server which only can be accesed by username and password. Access is only possible within the institution	951912-951894-102121962
Data are saved on the spectrometers PCs and automatically copied to institutional servers that backup data. Chemists have a dedicated space shared by a laboratory where they can	951912-951894-102129825

access their data and copy it to their machines. Biological NMR experts access and analyse their data on institutional servers with dedicated NMR software that we maintain	
We have a script to upload every day's new NMR data to the university share drive during midnight, which is managed by the facility. We can give users access to the drive. The users have read-only right in the share drive, but they can transfer the data to their computer to work on.	951912-951894-102130642
They access the data by AnyDesk software.	951912-951894-102134862
Using LOGS repository solution	951912-951894-102136549
nmr spectra are located on a specific nmr server (linux) working as a samba server. Each local user can access the data with a specific password. Access will be granted on basis of ip addresses.	951912-951894-102133983
data are saved on an university server and on a specific directory for each user	951912-951894-102138055
For local users : Data is written directly to a shared drive with user authentication. For external users : A secure download link is sent by the platform manager by mail.	951912-951894-102118767
NMR data kept secure on a local hard disk and a server. Internal user access their data via a ssh login. External user can copy they data on a disk under the control of their internal collaborator.	951912-951894-102156909
Individual account with specific login and password --> individual NMR data Access to user NMR data by securised FTP protocol	951912-951894-102165276
Different password-protected user accounts in Windows operation system and TopSpin/IconNMR programs. Local users have both local (onsite computer) and remote access (must have specific program and password). Industrial users have their own user account but their data are send to them - they don't have any direct access to the infrastructure.	951912-951894-102176888
Data is given to user using the secure file sender system, or on a physical device. The data is behind the firewall system and regular backups are made.	951912-951894-102291084

- 23** Prior to, during and since the Covid19 pandemic, did you provide remote access to one or more of the NMR spectrometers in your facility? By remote access, we mean that either: 1) users could directly operate the NMR spectrometer by remote login to the NMR spectrometer computer (direct remote access), or 2) users could communicate via a computer linkup (Zoom/Teams etc) or telephone with a local operator who controlled the NMR spectrometer based on the information provided by the remote user (assisted remote access), or 3) some other type of remote access.

23.a If you would like to provide more detailed information about your mode of remote spectrometer access then please fill in the text box.

Showing all 59 responses	
Initially allowed expert users to use TeamViewer but now use DWService. Non-expert users have no remote access (and don't need it) because the facility manager runs experiments for them.	951912-951894-101360820
teamviewer access but not generally allowed, only for selected users	951912-951894-101369358
Staff and selected users have credentials to access the spectrometers via VNC.	951912-951894-101376470
Bruker IconWeb	951912-951894-101376176
Over Iconnmr Webinterface	951912-951894-101397329
the option is only open to expert users. they can connect via teamviewer or vnc	951912-951894-101411307
FastViewer Licence	951912-951894-101421520
Direct remote access was provided via the software NoMachine	951912-951894-101445018
We have already done this since 2015. access software varies over time und upgrades	951912-951894-101521141
Teamviewer	951912-951894-101551625
Essentially to local users : Access via NoMachine servers = spectrometer (linux) clients = windows/apple users machine located in the lab Remote access outside the lab for users possible via vpn on the local machine	951912-951894-101564816
Even though my IT department would not like it, I use Anydesk to access the NMR computers. It is a very limited number of users who get this option. Sometimes a combination of Zoom and Anydesk was used to assist others.	951912-951894-101577839
secure VNC connection over VPN	951912-951894-101603924

Splashtop and Teamviewer remote desktop	951912-951894-101605905
We used guacamole solution which allow the remote control of the computer. It was open and free solution and permit to give some rights in term of access to equipment depending on computer or people.	951912-951894-101612738
The user can access the facility network using the university VPN. Direct remote access is available with VNC softwares (remote desktop in CENTOS)	951912-951894-101613468
Typically, the NMR spectrometer computer is plugged on the lab network. All computers from the lab can access the computer using ssh, sftp, vnc (with secured authentications). At home, we use a VPN which permits authentication to the lab network and access to the NMR spectrometer computer.	951912-951894-101614329
TeamViever	951912-951894-101613305
we use a software for remote access	951912-951894-101618364
NoMachine (NX protocol)	951912-951894-101644910
Remote access only for expert users (NMR facility manager mainly), using VNC or Windows remote desktop. No remote access for users.	951912-951894-101648927
Selected, experienced users have constant remote access.	951912-951894-101675332
VPN	951912-951894-101693660
Direct remote access only for local operators (NMR staff).	951912-951894-101708184
VNC server running on two spectrometers (500 & 800). VNC can be accessed from institute internal network only. Remote access possible by secure VPN into internal network. VNC control allowed only for experienced users.	951912-951894-101709365
vpn	951912-951894-101713028
We provided access through TeamViewer or through X2go. The local managers would either use the built-in chat features of teamviewer, or open a teams or zoom session on a personal device (laptop, iPad, etc.)	951912-951894-101737673
We used Teamviewer until the pandemic and then switched to AnyDesk during the pandemic because of the high costs of the Teamviewer license and the aggressive marketing of the company.	951912-951894-101741397
SSH tunnel and VNC	951912-951894-101745973
Remote access requires VPN + double remote desktop: If not on campus, the user needs to set up a VPN to the university. Using personal username and password, the user logs in to a virtual Windows computer. This requires approval by NMR staff. From the virtual computer, the user logs on to one of the spectrometer computers using a shared username and password. External users are provided a temporary account on the university network, or access the instruments via TeamView on the virtual computer.	951912-951894-101745527

Only expert users are allowed remote access.	
Direct remote access has been set up a few years ago for a disabled staff who cannot come easily to the NMR room. It would be available for other users if needed but such use has been restricted so far. Assisted remote access is made possible on an on-demand basis for access to manufacturers (Bruker, RS2D, Magritek) for collaboration and troubleshooting.	951912-951894-101768538
Teamviewer, anydesk were used.	951912-951894-101783128
direct access to spectrometers for advance users with anydesk application	951912-951894-101807038
For NMR group users	951912-951894-101818436
Double Windows Remote Desktop sessions. First one with a university account into a Windows server. The the second word session with a local account on the the acquisition computer.	951912-951894-101830371
AnyDesk	951912-951894-101865710
web interface of ICON-NMR (TOPSPIN, Bruker)	951912-951894-101903382
Anydesk and Zoom were most successful for direct and assisted access respectively.	951912-951894-101891636
for a short period, I provided remote access to only one spectrometer, using the NoMachine software; enabling remote access to another pc within the institute (all within our firewall).	951912-951894-101518991
About 15 local experts users from the institute could operate the spectrometers through VNC via a secured VPN connection	951912-951894-101957336
remote access t o spectrometers is provided via TeamViewer just for experienced users. All other users can access their data on demand remotely on shared platforms e.g Microsoft OneDrive.	951912-951894-101953004
Using the program Pulsesecure supplied and installed by our IT. In addition Teams or Zoom can then be used.	951912-951894-101966822
vnc over ssh has always been available to advanced users. Remote http access to IconNMR queues was enabled during the pandemic but is now disabled again.	951912-951894-102043034
Solution state: remote access to Windows machines. In principle could be shared with users, but currently only used by the facility manager for maintenance and method development.	951912-951894-102051473
The software which is used is Anydesk and NoMachine	951912-951894-102074778
Anydesk remote login to the departmental pc and from there provided vnc access to the spectrometer or using any desk solely.	951912-951894-102075878
A limited number of expert users can remotely connect to the spectrometers and do experiments during weekends via software such as Anydesk.	951912-951894-102094099
Direct remote access restricted to the scientists of the research team	951912-951894-102093469

operating the platform Exchange with the other users by E-mail or telephone.	
Users need to request remote access permission, and when that is granted they log into the spectrometers via Bastion which requires authentication via an app installed on a smartphone.	951912-951894-102119682
Usually users would send us samples to analyse with specific instructions what pulse sequence is required and the required settings. Problems, suggestions are discussed via email, phone or video link if appropriate.	951912-951894-102121962
We use ssh access (X2go) or VNC protocols for facility members and for well know biological NMR experts only	951912-951894-102129825
Only the expert users, facility manager and technician can have remote access.	951912-951894-102130642
Website for NMR sample submission - the spectrometer is run by a facility employee.	951912-951894-102136549
using teamviewer or equivalent	951912-951894-102138055
Direct access using NOMACHINE software	951912-951894-102149927
- The platform manager can remotely access all spectrometers through a vpn. - Local users can schedule their analysis remotely on a sample changer from the iconnmr web interface.	951912-951894-102118767
TeamViewer can be used but only for internal users	951912-951894-102156909
For expert NMR scientists, use of NX Client protocol of direct remote access	951912-951894-102165276
Remote access to the 500 MHz NMR spectrometer was possible even prior to the pandemic: specific category of users, under specific computer set-up (program, password, etc) could access (and still can) directly the instrument and check their experiment, set up another, collect data, etc.	951912-951894-102176888

23.b Why has remote access to spectrometers not been implemented in your facility? (select any that apply)

No demand for remote access from users.	0
There were no restrictions during the pandemic that prevented onsite use of spectrometers.	0
Too difficult to implement remote access.	0
IT security concerns made remote access impossible.	0
Other	0

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

23.b.i If you selected Other, please specify:

No responses

23.c The aim of the Remote-NMR project is to develop a common framework for remote spectrometer access taking into account best practice across the EU/UK. Standardized training for remote access will also be put in place. Once this has been completed, would your NMR facility be interested in implementing remote spectrometer access?

Yes	0
No	0

24 If your facility has provided any type of remote access then select 'Yes' to proceed to further questions about your implementation of remote access. If your facility has not provided any type of remote access then select 'No' to proceed to the end of the survey.

25 If you have provided remote access, what categories of users had remote access. (please select all that apply)

26 Overall, how many remote users has your facility had in the last 2-3 years?

27 Local users

Showing first 5 of 70 responses	
8 individuals from one group	951912-951894-101360820
15	951912-951894-101369358
1	951912-951894-101372382
<10	951912-951894-101376176
>20	951912-951894-101397329

28 National users

Showing first 5 of 44 responses	
0	951912-951894-101360820
3	951912-951894-101372382
0	951912-951894-101376176
0	951912-951894-101397329
0	951912-951894-101521141

29 Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide)

Showing first 5 of 38 responses	
0	951912-951894-101360820
0	951912-951894-101372382
0	951912-951894-101376176
0	951912-951894-101397329
0	951912-951894-101521141

30 Industrial users

Showing first 5 of 42 responses	
0	951912-951894-101360820
0	951912-951894-101372382
0	951912-951894-101376176
0	951912-951894-101397329
0	951912-951894-101521141

31 What type of spectrometers were available for remote access? (select all that apply)

31.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing 1 response	
Magritek RS2D	951912-951894-101768538

32 What software was used for remote access? (select all that apply)

32.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 42 responses	
DWService	951912-951894-101360820
VNC	951912-951894-101376470
Bruker IconWeb or MS remote desktop	951912-951894-101376176
Iconnmr Webinterface	951912-951894-101397329
vnc	951912-951894-101411307
FastViewer	951912-951894-101421520
google sharing software for a while, but are currently using AnyDesk.	951912-951894-101521141
VNC	951912-951894-101601534
Splashtop	951912-951894-101605905
Guacamole	951912-951894-101612738
VNC software with VPN access	951912-951894-101613468
vncviewer Remmina Vnc client in MacOS	951912-951894-101614329
microsoft remote desktop with VPN	951912-951894-101617105
VNC	951912-951894-101642396
Remote desktop	951912-951894-101675332
VPN	951912-951894-101693660
SSH tunneling through firewall server and then Windows Remote Desktop Connection.	951912-951894-101708184
VNC server. We have experimented with TeamViewer, but could not work out a scenario that everyone would have been happy with.	951912-951894-101709365
	951912-951894-101745973

SSH tunnel and VNC	
Windows Remote Desktop	951912-951894-101745527
putty/VNCviewer	951912-951894-101647177
Guacamole	951912-951894-101768538
Windows Remote Desktop twice. One on top of another. See another answer.	951912-951894-101830371
vnc	951912-951894-101849988
dwservice VNC	951912-951894-101795121
Bomgar Remote Support (BeyondTrust)	951912-951894-101897907
ICON NMR Webinterface	951912-951894-101903382
NoMachine	951912-951894-101518991
VNC via an ssh tunnel	951912-951894-101943180
VNC via a secured VPN	951912-951894-101957336
PulseSecure	951912-951894-101966822
VNC viewer	951912-951894-101902953
vnc (tunnelled over ssh)	951912-951894-102043034
Formerly using TeamViewer, then Remote Utilities, then AnyDesk, and now currently on NoMachine in combination with TailScale to punch through the university firewall.	951912-951894-102051473
VNC	951912-951894-102075878
Access via VNC under VPN connexion	951912-951894-102093469
Bastion	951912-951894-102119682
ssh: X2go vnc server	951912-951894-102129825
VNC viewer	951912-951894-102130642
remote desktop connexion	951912-951894-102136549
remote access via vpn (rdp)	951912-951894-102133983
iconnmr web interface (bruker)	951912-951894-102118767

33 Did local IT staff place any restrictions on remote user access to ensure network security (select all that apply)?

33.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 10 responses	
What they don't know won't harm them...	951912-951894-101360820
Password only given to limited number of people	951912-951894-101421520
I am pretty sure the university IT would say "don't". Did not dare to ask.	951912-951894-101577839
Cisco AnyConnect Secure Mobility Client	951912-951894-101647177
No restrictions	951912-951894-101834048
Member of a special active directory group	951912-951894-101897907
Verified users can use short-term login from a static IP,	951912-951894-101902953
TailScale requires authentication, and setup to use university MS/O365 credentials.	951912-951894-102051473
remote access was provided after setting up the experiments. So first test power, spinning etc and remotely continue the experiment	951912-951894-102075878
Selected categories of users (only highest ones). Daily password that the user had to collect by physical presence in the facility or by contacting the NMR SuperUser	951912-951894-102176888

34 Did login procedures for remote users differ from those for on-site users?

34.a If yes, how did remote users login?

34.a.i If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 6 responses	
via FastViewer	951912-951894-101421520
Remote users required VPN account while on-site users do not.	951912-951894-101359111
The remote user worked under a login of a facility staff member.	951912-951894-101640129
Login to remote access server via active directory account	951912-951894-101897907
Short-term account with open access to other users' files	951912-951894-101902953
Users needed to login to Bastion via two-step authentication, but after that they had the same access as they were sitting at the spectrometer.	951912-951894-102119682

35 Were remote users provided with support by local NMR facility staff?

35.a If yes, what type of support was provided? (select all that apply)

35.a.i If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 4 responses	
remote access was allowed only for NMR facility staff	951912-951894-101683781
Industrial access was for NMR manufacturers, therefore it was rather them helping our staff than our staff helping them!	951912-951894-101768538
Zoom support - a live session between two national users and facility staff for example	951912-951894-101891636
Only the staff directly access to the spectrometer, remotely or not. The users can only at most be allowed to put their sample on the carroussel but are never allowed to operate this spectrometer.	951912-951894-102136549

36 How were users' NMR samples loaded into spectrometers? (select all that apply)

36.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 3 responses	
For this part : Spectrometers are working in automatique mode (ICNOMNR) so users put their own samples on the sampler changer and manage their experiments in remote mode	951912-951894-101613305
Facility staff loaded NMR samples left behind by the user at the previous visit.	951912-951894-101640129
Users put their own samples on a sample changer kept at 4°C and can run their own experiments. Only facility members and well-known experts use remote access. We also run remotely experiments for non-experts in biological NMR	951912-951894-102129825

37 Are spectrometers available for remote access equipped with automatic sample changers and were these important for provision of remote access?

37.a If yes, please indicate the make/model of sample changer.

Showing all 60 responses	
BACS SampleCase	951912-951894-101369358
Samplejet (with cooling option)	951912-951894-101372382
BACS-60 SampleXpress	951912-951894-101376470
Bruker SampleJet or BACS-60	951912-951894-101376176
BACS 60 SampleXpress	951912-951894-101397329
SampleJet	951912-951894-101411307
SampleCase and BACS	951912-951894-101445018
Bruker cooled 24x samplejet	951912-951894-101521141
SampleJet SampleCase	951912-951894-101577839
SampleCase	951912-951894-101601534
Bruker SampleJet Bruker SampleCase	951912-951894-101605905
Sample jet for the 2 spectrometers	951912-951894-101612738
Bruker sampleCase + sampleXpress 60 (400MHz) and 16 positions (500MHz)	951912-951894-101613468
Bruker SampleXpress	951912-951894-101617105
SampleJet with temp controlled racks accommodating 3mm or 5mm tubes.	951912-951894-101359111
ASC30 JEOL	951912-951894-101642396
A 24 sample, random-access, automation system	951912-951894-101675332
Bruker BACS 60 and sample case	951912-951894-101683781

Bruker BACS 60 and sample case	951912-951894-101693660
BACS60	951912-951894-101693660
B-ACS 60	951912-951894-101708184
Bruker BACS60; Varian SMS50	951912-951894-101709365
BACS 60, SampleJet (temperature controlled), SampleCase	951912-951894-101725463
B-ACS 60 SampleCase 24	951912-951894-101728276
SampleJet	951912-951894-101741397
samplejet and samplecase	951912-951894-101745973
SampleJet	951912-951894-101745527
Bruker BACS	951912-951894-101752958
Sample case with 24 sample holders.	951912-951894-101647177
Bruker SampleJet Magritek Sample changer	951912-951894-101768538
BACS60 Samplejet	951912-951894-101807038
BACS 120 BACS 60 Sample Jet	951912-951894-101830371
Standard SampleCase carousel with 24 positions	951912-951894-101834048
Bruker SampleJet (cooling only versions to +6c, and latest variable temperature versions, depending on spectrometer)	951912-951894-101849988
SampleXpress SampleCase	951912-951894-101795121
SampleJet	951912-951894-101897907
Sample Express	951912-951894-101903382
Room temperature SampleJet (Bruker) c. 2015 (600MHz) Chilled SampleJet (Bruker) c. 2013 (700MHz) Chilled SampleJet (Bruker) c. 2018 (800MHz)	951912-951894-101891636
SampleXpress SampleCase	951912-951894-101943180
Non refrigerated Samplecase with 24 holders on 2 out of 6 spectrometers	951912-951894-101957336
Bruker SampleXpress & SampleCase	951912-951894-101953004
SampleCase cooled	951912-951894-101966822
Bruker SampleJet.	951912-951894-101902953
BACS 60 SampleXpress SampleCase+	951912-951894-102043034
SampleXpress	951912-951894-102051473

Bruker Sample Case 16 positions	951912-951894-102074778
Bruker SampleCase Bruker SAmpleXpressLite	951912-951894-102094099
A cooled samplejet is available on the 600MHz equipped with cryoprobes.	951912-951894-102093469
SampleCase 24-slot	951912-951894-102119682
Bruker SampleCase 24 positions on 800/600 MHz spectrometers	951912-951894-102129825
SampleJet, SampleExpress	951912-951894-102130642
Bruker NMR Case	951912-951894-102134862
SampleXpress	951912-951894-102136549
sample case 24	951912-951894-102133983
samplejet	951912-951894-102138055
Bruker SampleCase Plus	951912-951894-102149927
4 spectrometers (2 300MHz and 2 500MHz spectrometers) are equipped with BACS60 sample changers.	951912-951894-102118767
SampleXpress from BRUKER	951912-951894-102165276
Bruker	951912-951894-102176888
Bruker SampleCase	951912-951894-102291084

37.b If yes, was the sample changer temperature controlled (i.e. are samples stored at a specified temperature before insertion in the spectrometer)?

38 Was remote access restricted to users with specific levels of expertise or were all user categories able to access spectrometers remotely?

38.a If remote access was restricted to users with specific levels of expertise then please specify which category(ies) of users?

Showing all 59 responses	
Expert users only (i.e. the ones who use the machines themselves anyway and who can now just login from home to check it's all ticking over nicely).	951912-951894-101360820
users with prior experience running spectrometers on their own	951912-951894-101369358
This was done on an ad-hoc basis, based on an assessment of user skill, rather than any formalised category.	951912-951894-101372382
Remote access was granted only to users with spectrometer operation training (above ordinary open access)	951912-951894-101376470
Advanced users with training	951912-951894-101376176
expert	951912-951894-101411307
People predominantly working with NMR spectroscopy = experienced users	951912-951894-101421520
Post-doctoral workers or equivalent and academic members of staff	951912-951894-101445018
minimum level 1, but then restricted use.	951912-951894-101521141
Certain pulse sequence development cannot done be remotely.	
Local users trained at the lab External users: experts only	951912-951894-101564816
Very experienced users	951912-951894-101577839
Any user trained beyond the basic requirements for 'walk-up' access to our open shop iconnmr 300MHz	951912-951894-101605905
Only for "expert" users	951912-951894-101613468
Users with strong background in NMR (assistant professor, Post-doc, PhD student, etc.)	951912-951894-101614329
users who known what to do (after a formation)	951912-951894-101613305
phd in nmr, researcher, engineer, prof and assistant prof	951912-951894-101617105
Expert users only known to the facility staff.	951912-951894-101640129
Local users	951912-951894-101642396
Highly skilled (proven!) professionals	951912-951894-101675332
High level required	951912-951894-101693660
NMR staff (selected)	951912-951894-101708184
Advanced/Experienced users only; generally people who know what they are doing and are unlikely to generate problems.	951912-951894-101709365
expert users only	951912-951894-101713028

As a rule only to internal users	951912-951894-101725463
scientific researchers	951912-951894-101728276
There was generally an experienced user who took control of the spectrometer. It was generally self-regulating.	951912-951894-101737673
Users with NMR expertise	951912-951894-101741397
Those who wanted it, and requested info about the SSH/VNC route	951912-951894-101745973
Expert users	951912-951894-101745527
Only expert users are allowed for remote access.	951912-951894-101647177
Advanced users for very specific cases (disabled researcher or specialists at NMR manufacturers)	951912-951894-101768538
Standard users. NMR Lab staff only	951912-951894-101783128
any except industrial users	951912-951894-101807038
Selected based on managers trust in individuals	951912-951894-101830371
Standard users (can select from a wider list of experiments but cannot run their own pulse sequences) and Expert users (can run any experiments and write their own pulse sequences)	951912-951894-101834048
Expert users only.	951912-951894-101849988
Expert	951912-951894-101865710
Independent users who had been trained in remote operation and could not access the spectrometers on-site	951912-951894-101891636
expert users	951912-951894-101518991
Expert and advanced local users	951912-951894-101943180
local expert users from the institute	951912-951894-101957336
experienced users	951912-951894-101953004
Expert level users that can operate the spectrometer unaided	951912-951894-101966822
Only trusted users with expertise in Bruker NMR experimental setups were allowed.	951912-951894-101902953
Facility manager	951912-951894-102051473
Expert users only	951912-951894-102073777
experts NMR users	951912-951894-102074778
Again, expert users running for example metabolomics projects were granted remote access if requested.	951912-951894-102094099
Only local scientists of the platform research team can nowadays access remotely to the spectrometers. This could be extended to experienced users in the future.	951912-951894-102093469

facility members and well-known local NMR experts	951912-951894-102129825
Expert users, facility manager and technician	951912-951894-102130642
Only expertised person can use our spectrometer with remote control.	951912-951894-102134862
only the facility staff can (remotely or not) operate the spectrometer, but anyone can ask for measurement time on this spectrometer.	951912-951894-102136549
expert users only	951912-951894-102133983
expert users, not occasional users	951912-951894-102138055
Only for local users who received a training.	951912-951894-102118767
Remote access only for expert users	951912-951894-102165276
Highest levels with more experience - usually PhD candidates and post-docs of synthetic organic and synthetic inorganic teams	951912-951894-102176888
Users with a vast experience on operating NMR spectrometers at the facility.	951912-951894-102291084

39 How was the NMR data collected by remote users protected and/or kept secure and did the procedures differ from those in place for on-site users? (please specify)

Showing all 67 responses	
No difference at all.	951912-951894-101360820
no difference, no protection	951912-951894-101369358
Data backup and security process was identical for on-site users.	951912-951894-101372382
Access procedure differed.	
Procedures did not differ	951912-951894-101376470
Same as non remote acquisitions	951912-951894-101376176
no difference	951912-951894-101397329
retrieve data from server or ask facility manager to send data over	951912-951894-101411307
No difference to on-site users	951912-951894-101445018
no	951912-951894-101521141
Back up on local server in the lab every week No difference between local and external users	951912-951894-101564816
No difference	951912-951894-101577839
Remote users are also local users. Same guidelines apply.	951912-951894-101601534
emailed directly from iconnmr data uploaded to network server	951912-951894-101605905
no different to on-site users	

It's the same DMP for remote or on-site users	951912-951894-101612738
Same procedure (even in local access, they must use SFTP to access their data). The only difference is the use of VPN	951912-951894-101613468
same procedures as on site user	951912-951894-101613305
can't remove or write on existing folders, just download	951912-951894-101617105
Procedures the same for all users. Login to the spectrometers from outside our department network requires a local VPN account. In person access to the NMR facility is limited to people with a keycard to enter the building.	951912-951894-101359111
Data collected under the facility member account, then securely transferred to the user via FileSender.	951912-951894-101640129
No difference between them	951912-951894-101642396
The data kept on password-protected NAS, no difference for in place users	951912-951894-101644910
procedure was the same.	951912-951894-101675332
data were collected as usual on a network drive. spectra were done by NMR facility staff	951912-951894-101683781
Remote users data are collected through a data transfer system as for the on-site users	951912-951894-101693660
The procedure is the same. User NMR data is kept on a web server where each user group (project or lab, etc.) has its own account that only allows access to its data.	951912-951894-101708184
Same as for on site users. VPN access to internal data server.	951912-951894-101709365
not different from on-site users	951912-951894-101713028
Procedures are the same: data are accessible only by the user logged in the spectrometer and by the administrator	951912-951894-101725463
The nmr data was saved on a server	951912-951894-101728276
The access password was supposed to change for each user (but did not due to issues with permissions on TeamViewers side) The security was the same for all users.	951912-951894-101737673
As data for most of the users was recorded by the on-site staff, the on-site staff kept data secure.	951912-951894-101741397
No	951912-951894-101745973
For some external remote users, the data was compressed and shared via a link sent by email.	951912-951894-101745527
Data collected are stored on Nas drive. The procedures were same.	951912-951894-101752958
No special procedures are applied. Data can be accessed and downloaded directly from the NMR site. But every day the data are mirror imaged to a server for archiving and later download.	951912-951894-101647177
Procedure did not differ from on-site users	951912-951894-101783128

all data are saved onto two data servers	951912-951894-101807038
No difference	951912-951894-101830371
No, the procedures do not differ	951912-951894-101834048
Same procedure as for on-site users. Data transferred across to user's local workstation using ssh, and/or stored on the local secure facility data server.	951912-951894-101849988
Normal way. The procedures do not differ.	951912-951894-101865710
No difference to on-site users.	951912-951894-101897907
no difference to on-site users	951912-951894-101903382
Same procedures as for on-site users	951912-951894-101891636
same procedures	951912-951894-101518991
Remote users are local users so no difference	951912-951894-101943180
NMR data fro remote users are transfered via a web service (filesender) Local users can access their files on the spectrometers via NFS	951912-951894-101957336
remote users data been transfer on OneDrive folders available just to defined users.	951912-951894-101953004
Same procedure, the user is responsible for the data.	951912-951894-101966822
the same as for in-house users	951912-951894-101902953
ICON did all the data handling for the majority of users. other users had only access to certain drives for data storage, based on their account credentials.	951912-951894-102043034
All interaction via IconNMR as normal - no difference.	951912-951894-102051473
Secure shell access	951912-951894-102073777
no specific procedure	951912-951894-102074778
same procedure as local users, i.e. sftp, wetransfer.	951912-951894-102075878
NMR data collected by remote users were treated the same as on-site users.	951912-951894-102094099
No difference between remote and on-site users.	951912-951894-102093469
The same rules applied as for on-site users.	951912-951894-102119682
The procedures are the same.	951912-951894-102130642
They removed their data by the AnyDesk software.	951912-951894-102134862
automatic loading onto our repository	951912-951894-102136549
The same way as on site	951912-951894-102133983
from university server with restricted access	951912-951894-102138055
No difference to on-site use	951912-951894-102149927
No difference with on-site users.	951912-951894-102118767

The use of VPN is essential for remote data retrieval.	
NMR data secured by VPN (individual VPN login/password) for the remote access and individual account for monitoring AVIII500 spectrometer.	951912-951894-102165276
The procedure is the same for both remote and on-site access.	951912-951894-102176888

40 What bottlenecks or other problems did you identify in providing remote spectrometer access?

Showing all 66 responses	
<p>The same one I always have for non-expert users: I'm only one person and part of my job involves teaching so at some times of the year it can take me months to get round to running a sample.</p> <p>The expert users are also a lot more reluctant to come into the building in person if they aren't changing a sample, which means they're not around to mop up spare machine time when it arises.</p>	951912-951894-101360820
number of teamviewer licenses	951912-951894-101369358
None	951912-951894-101376470
<p>If something went wrong, difficult to diagnose. Someone had to be on site.</p> <p>Bugs with IconWeb software.</p>	951912-951894-101376176
worked out okay.	951912-951894-101397329
the main concern is that when something went wrong the remote user may not realise it quick enough.	951912-951894-101411307
Not all probes are ATM therefore some local manual intervention is required	951912-951894-101445018
stability of internet connection, changing programs and issues with updates and compatibility	951912-951894-101521141
<p>Quality of internet speed</p> <p>For external users : problem of confidentiality due to the same user account for everyone -> how to separate accounts properly with rights/permissions in linux?</p>	951912-951894-101564816
<p>Multiple remote connections makes controls slow</p> <p>IT security is a problem</p> <p>Instrument errors were more difficult to control and handle</p>	951912-951894-101577839
Sample storage. And malfunctions that require local interventions.	951912-951894-101601534
managing Splashtop licenses and access for a site license shared across multiple analytical facilities	951912-951894-101605905
<p>I didn't see problems with remote access. At the beginning it was mainly to managers of the platform but sincèrement COVID pandemic it was extended to all users and allow to run and take care of spectrometers and users. We will continue to go on this direction for national and internantionnal collaboration to contribute in a way in the reduction of GES avoiding some travel for the future</p>	951912-951894-101612738

<p>SES avoiding some travel for the future. The only things that It's important It's the presence on site of dedicated engineer in case of problem (communication, sample carrier etc...)</p>	
Limitation to the access of the VPN for people of other departments	951912-951894-101613468
Access to the VPN required a university account.	951912-951894-101614329
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sample transfert - skill of users - data 	951912-951894-101613305
problems with the installation of vpn depend on the person used a linux mac or windows.	951912-951894-101617105
<p>Most of the remote users were locally based so were able to put their own samples into the spectrometer or to drop them off in the building.</p> <p>We offer remote access to users at other universities. They overwhelmingly prefer to travel to our site with their samples rather than risking sending the samples via courier. For shorter trips it is probably cheaper to travel by train than to send samples by courier.</p>	951912-951894-101359111
<p>You must trust the expertise of the remote user. A staff member must be at hand at all times in case the remote user needs some physical manipulation with the sample or spectrometer.</p>	951912-951894-101640129
None	951912-951894-101642396
Lack of sample changer	951912-951894-101644910
na	951912-951894-101675332
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - one NMR facility staff was on site to put the samples in the sample changer - online analysis requests were set up, it was difficult and expensive because we have no IT staff to program it 	951912-951894-101683781
The procedure is not very user-friendly.	951912-951894-101708184
<p>Some users seem to be more prone to mistyping or miss-clicking when working remote.</p> <p>External users may be working with the spectrometer at any time of day; is there is an unexpected fault, they may seek assistance at any time of day.</p> <p>Both autosampler systems developed malfunctions during the CoViD period. This cased serious throughput limitations, repairs took unexpectedly long.</p> <p>Failing or unreliable internet connection may force spectrometer PC into surprising states sometimes.</p>	951912-951894-101709365
no bottlenecks	951912-951894-101713028
<p>Speed of connection</p> <p>Lack of possibility to select/assign expertise levels to remote users depending on the TopSpin version</p> <p>Additional personnel necessary for sample preparation/handling</p> <p>Uncertainty of time of delivering, risk for sample degradation due to delays are the main hindering issues from the user's side</p>	951912-951894-101725463
sometimes the autosampler crashed. or you had to restart the software or	951912-951894-101728276

<p>sometimes the autosampler crashed, or you had to restart the software on the workstation.</p>	
<p>TeamViewer passwords are not always set properly in Linux. The availability of the local operator was a bottleneck. Sample changes and spinning up samples could be a burden on the local operator since many users expectations are possible when in person, but not for someone running multiple spectrometers. There is also an underestimation of the work that a local operator may be putting in when troubles appear, as it all happens "off-camera". Shipping of the samples also did not always line up with the expectations of one party or another.</p>	951912-951894-101737673
<p>No major bottlenecks yet as most of the experiments were ran by on-site staff.</p>	951912-951894-101741397
<p>Our route is a bit laboured, but quite secure to satisfy local IT</p>	951912-951894-101745973
<p>There is an issue (memory leak) with the spectrometer running Windows 7 and Topspin 3.6. While using remote access, TopSpin becomes gradually slower, until it is not usable any more. The only solution is to close Topspin, log out of the computer, log in again and restart Topspin. This is problematic when running long experiments.</p> <p>Tightened IT security at the university makes it more difficult to have temporary accounts for external users.</p>	951912-951894-101745527
<p>No</p>	951912-951894-101752958
<p>Sample identification and avoiding sample exchange by mistake.</p>	951912-951894-101647177
<p>Setting up secured protocols that match the institutional regulations Convincing the NMR facility staff that this is acceptable practice (psychological barrier)</p>	951912-951894-101768538
<p>No bottleneck</p>	951912-951894-101783128
<p>Sometime problems with sample changer that require the presence of a local operator</p>	951912-951894-101807038
<p>None</p>	951912-951894-101830371
<p>Remote users not always remembering to advise facility staff when they've finished measuring/completed their booking, so that staff can log users out of the spectrometer. NMR time is charged based on login time. We advise users not to log out remotely unless they are 100% sure the sample has been removed from the magnet successfully. In practice, this means relying on facility staff to check sample removal/log users out.</p>	951912-951894-101849988
<p>Sometimes there is an urgent need to manually change samples, restart the autosampler.</p>	951912-951894-101795121
<p>Instability of remote access software (hanging updates).</p>	951912-951894-101897907
<p>Anydesk not terribly secure - only used sparingly as we really need to avoid multiple users connecting remotely simultaneously.</p> <p>It became clear that local users would attempt to use anydesk to view spectr outside their booked slot - creating issues fro users who were trying to operate the spectrometer at the same time.</p>	951912-951894-101891636

Our current solution/workaround is to change the Anydesk password frequently (weekly) to ensure only booked remote users can access. We do not have explicit permission from the universities IT services (Anydesk avoids the need for VPN etc so no formal IT support from University is not required).	
Rights management, data security, local network security	951912-951894-101943180
We limit remote access to the spectrometers because of the following two issues. - Network security issues - The lack of interaction between the platform staff and the remote users which can lead to damage to the spectrometers (difficulty to assess the level of expertise of the users).	951912-951894-101957336
Not everything is possible to do remotely without being familiar with the system - particularly high field spectrometers. From my point of view on one side is great to give access to 800 MHz spectrometer to wide nmr community but on other side it's still quite a time consuming for me as not all of the users are enough experienced to use the spectrometer (Bruker Neo console with TS4.1) on their own.	951912-951894-101953004
Attempts to teach about NMR remotely using both PulseSecure from a laptop to control the spectrometer host and Teams/Zoom to interact with a group of users generally suffered from the interactive controls being too slow to use in any meaningful way.	951912-951894-101966822
1. Users has problems on their own side with VNC viewer/internet etc. 2. Multiple users could be logged in at the same time 3. When solving issue 2, a first user not logging out could hinder another user to log in 4. Personal support from staff onsite necessary, especially for handling changes between manual insertion and SampleJet runs, and to aid in non-standard procedures e.g. handling of BCU setups for temperature regulation 5. In principle, staff on duty was necessary at all times to handle issues in TopSpin etc. which the users had not encountered before	951912-951894-101902953
Clashes between remote users and local users. Samples being removed. Software bugs making entire queues get lost.	951912-951894-102043034
User expertise Rack space to accommodate more samples	951912-951894-102051473
Samples change	951912-951894-102073777
no problems	951912-951894-102074778
control of spinning stabilities using manual spinning, measuring power in-between experiments, screen resolution	951912-951894-102075878
One of our two spectrometers with remote access has an aged computer, so slow connection speed and response delays were a concern sometimes.	951912-951894-102094099
- IT restrictions for secure access - The installation of a secured remote access need human IT resources	951912-951894-102093469

The installation of a secured remote access need human IT resources that are lacking at the moment.	
A user can only start one Bastion session, i.e. one cannot log into the spectrometer computer both from home and from his office.	951912-951894-102119682
None	951912-951894-102129825
The facility manager or technician has to be always on-site in case of troubleshooting unexpected error during remote measurement. There is still not sample changer available for micro imaging. So the users have to place the samples manually and measure remotely. This is not convenient when the users have multiple samples to measure.	951912-951894-102130642
The instability of network can be a problem, but the most serious if some electricity stop happen. In this case restart is only possible with personal attendance.	951912-951894-102134862
Sample changer errors - for ex. sample stuck in the BST	951912-951894-102136549
the Topspin on the spectrometer's control workstation had to be closed (or PID/PPID had to killed) to run Topspin remotely.	951912-951894-102133983
security problems with the university IT. have staff close to the machines to introduce the samples and solve any problems	951912-951894-102138055
Data transfer sometimes slow, most likely due to internet connection speed	951912-951894-102149927
- IT restrictions for secure access - The installation of a secured remote access need human IT resources that are lacking at the moment. - The research unit is under french defense ministry control, which restrict the access of non-local users.	951912-951894-102118767
Only one connexion per user. Multisession not available even for NMR processing	951912-951894-102165276
Troubleshooting in case of problems with the instrument or the computer outside of working hours,	951912-951894-102176888
-Sometimes slow response times; -Lack of suitable VPN/Remote Desktop for certain operating systems	951912-951894-102291084

41 If your facility has a webpage with information about remote access please enter the URL below.

Showing all 21 responses	
N/A	951912-951894-101360820
N/A	951912-951894-101376176
internal access only.....sorry	951912-951894-101605905
Not for the moment	951912-951894-101612738
N/A	951912-951894-101642396
na	951912-951894-101675332
no	951912-951894-101693660
No.	951912-951894-101708184
NA	951912-951894-101709365
https://www.cerm.unifi.it/access-to-cerm-cirmmp/18-access/192-remote-access	951912-951894-101725463
https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/sci/physics/research/condensedmatt/nmr/	951912-951894-101737673
No	951912-951894-101752958
Not applicable	951912-951894-101647177
kjemi.uio.no/nmr. deep in there somewhere	951912-951894-101830371
Not available yet	951912-951894-101834048
Anydesk use is not promoted	951912-951894-101891636
No	951912-951894-102073777
No	951912-951894-102093469
no	951912-951894-102133983
n/a	951912-951894-102149927
no	951912-951894-102165276

42 Is your facility continuing to provide remote access to NMR spectrometers now that some/many/all 'pandemic' restrictions have been lifted?

43 If you have further information that you would like to provide, please enter this in the text box below.

Showing all 15 responses	
regarding the login question: teamviewer does not require a login, but a registration at the teamviewer server, so the IT is not necessarily involved, we manage the teamviewer access ourself	951912-951894-101369358
No more information	951912-951894-101612738
Remote-NMR sounds as a great project, especially for facilities like us with lots of analysis time available	951912-951894-101614329
N/A	951912-951894-101642396
na	951912-951894-101675332
Remote access was not a result of covid and lockdown. We had remote access prior to covid. During covid there was not an increase in remote access, as the users had access to the NMR lab most of the time, except for a few short periods.	951912-951894-101745527
In summary, Remote access at our site is possible, but in practice its use is restricted to 2 specific cases: -disabled researcher -access for NMR companies to perform collaborative work (development) and troubleshooting	951912-951894-101768538
Equality Inclusion and Diversity is the main reason we wish to keep remote access as an option. We have researchers with childcare issue (and indeed immunocompromised facility users) where remote access may be more appropriate. Ideally we need a solution that can be locked to a specific user for a specific account before we can roll out remote access more widely. In particular we are somewhat hamstrung by restrictions that the universities IT services impose (although we appreciate the need for secure systems we have chosen Anydesk not as it is most fit for purpose but because it circumvents university IT restrictions)	951912-951894-101891636
We are running national Scottish High Field NMR Facility under SNUG initiative already for about 3 years giving local & remote access to other places in Scotland (https://www.snug.ac.uk/). These institutions are getting 50% of 800 spectrometer time between them. I believe it makes a big impact to these institutions to have access to high resolution & sensitivity spectrometer. They can run their experiments either by themselves locally or remotely or use the automation. Data are archived by the end on Microsoft OneDrive with access limited just to defined users. As mentioned before from my point of view on one side is great to give access to 800 to wide Scottish nmr community but on other side it's still quite a time consuming for me as not all of the users are enough experienced to use the spectrometer (Bruker Neo console with TS4.1) on their own.	951912-951894-101953004
It at least added versatility to our expert users who could monitor and adjust experiments remotely. Attempts to teach using remote access were mostly unsuccessful, but this could be improved by a more direct form of remote control. Our IT	951912-951894-101966822

department however blocked the use of software like Teamviewer and similar direct remote access applications.	
Remote access has worked well for us, and it has been used a lot by the personell at the NMR center themselves, when working from home. We benefitted from having it all setup prior to lock downs, and could easily switch to a remote working mode.	951912-951894-101902953
Bastion is great, much better than Teamviewer.	951912-951894-102119682
We cannot give direct remote access due to IT restrictions. We also would not let users unknown to us operate instruments directly. An operator must be present at all times. We have good experinece with assistent remote access where users send us samples and we discuss any requirements and set-ups with them. This can be done when the experiment is running	951912-951894-102121962
One spectrometer is open-access but no remote access; the other one is only remotely accessible.	951912-951894-102136549
remote access is limited to a few experienced users as we do not have any external requests. as our system is in a GMP environment, access is strictly limited to authorised persons. however, we regularly carry out measurements for external members but with the control of our qualified personnel	951912-951894-102138055

APPENDIX 4

Remote-NMR (R-NMR): Moving NMR infrastructures to remote access capabilities

NMR FACILITY MANAGER SURVEY (2-24 November 2022)

Univ. of Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee Approval Reference: [R77838/RE001]

SUMMARY OF RESPONSES FROM NMR FACILITIES NOT PROVIDING REMOTE ACCESS

Introduction

Lockdown restrictions in many countries during 2020-2021 Covid19 pandemic resulted in the implementation of remote access to NMR spectrometers as a way of enabling the continuation of important research. The experiences of several European NMR facilities during the pandemic have shown that this access mode can work well within the field of NMR spectroscopy. It is the aim of the Remote-NMR project to develop and exploit remote access to NMR facilities. Work Package 2 within R-NMR focusses on the “Remote NMR Landscape”. Task 2.1 within WP2 is a review of current protocols in place for remote access to NMR facilities, including statistics on current implementation of remote access. This information has been collected via an online survey of NMR facility managers.

This document is a summary of the subset of responses from 59 NMR facility managers at facilities that did not provide remote access to their NMR spectrometers.

Remote-NMR: NMR Facility Manager Survey

Showing 59 of 142 responses

Showing **all** responses

Hiding **20** questions

With filter **q23-is-no** applied

- 1** You are invited to complete this online survey aimed at NMR facility managers. We will ask questions about your NMR facility, your experiences with providing remote access to NMR spectrometers and for your views on how remote access can be improved in the future. The survey can be completed without providing your name or contact email address but you will be asked to indicate in which country your NMR facility is located. There will be the option to provide more detailed information via a one-to-one online interview; in this case you will be asked to provide your name/email address so that you can be contacted directly. Information that you provide about your experiences with remote access will be included in discussions with other R-NMR project participants and in project reports; however this information will not be associated with your name or your email address. All survey data will be stored at the University of Oxford on a secure computer (password protected and behind a firewall) during the duration of the R-NMR project (until 30 June 2025). An anonymised version of the survey (without any name/email information) will be created for longer-term storage. We intend to keep this version for 3 years after publication of the outcome of the project. Please confirm below: That you have read this information, and if you require further detailed information, that you have read the Participant Information Sheet. That you understand who will have access to any personal data that you provide, how data will be stored and what will happen to data at the end of the project. That you understand how to raise a concern or make a complaint. That you are willing to continue with the survey.

Yes 59 (100%)
No | 0

- 2** Please confirm that you are the manager of an NMR facility. (Please try to ensure that the survey is only completed by one person involved in the management of your NMR facility).

Yes 59 (100%)
No | 0

- 3** In which country is your NMR facility located? Select one:

3.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing 1 response	
Canada	951912-951894-101613960

4 Is your NMR facility part of a national infrastructure?

5 How many spectrometers do you have in your NMR facility?

6 At what 1H frequencies do your spectrometers operate? (select all that apply)

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

7 What type of spectrometers do you have in your facility? (select all that apply)

Multi answer: Percentage of respondents who selected each answer option (e.g. 100% would represent that all this question's respondents chose that option)

7.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 4 responses	
Magritek Benchtop	951912-951894-101369602
Magritech	951912-951894-101614904
Magritek	951912-951894-101742975
Magritek	951912-951894-102109484

8 What data acquisition software do your spectrometers run? (select all that apply)

8.a If you selected Bruker TopSpin, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 51 responses	
1.3 3.2 3.5.6 3.6.1 4.1.3	951912-951894-101369602
TS3.6.x TS1.3	951912-951894-101370884
3.6.5	951912-951894-101397499
TS2 TS3	951912-951894-101401907
Topspin 3.2 Topspin 4.1	951912-951894-101524313

8.b If you selected Bruker IconNMR, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing first 5 of 17 responses	
4.0.7 4.7.7 5.0.6 5.0.9 5.2.3.1	951912-951894-101369602
5	951912-951894-101397499
3.6.5 4.1.4	951912-951894-101559699
4.7.1	951912-951894-101560777
4.2 5.0	951912-951894-101613339

8.c If you selected Agilent Vnmrj, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing all 6 responses	
openVnmrj	951912-951894-101550127
4.0	951912-951894-101728393
Vnmrj 2.2.D Vnmrj 3.1.A	951912-951894-101801357
3.1	951912-951894-101936205
VNMRJ 3.2	951912-951894-102078028
Openvnmrj version 3.1 A	951912-951894-102074887

8.d If you selected JEOL Delta, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing all 4 responses	
Delta 5.X Delta 5.X	951912-951894-101550127
Delta 5.3.1	951912-951894-101644803
Jeol Delta v6.2	951912-951894-102074887
v5.3.3	951912-951894-102131754

8.e If you selected GE/Omega, please specify the version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

No responses

8.f If you selected Other, please specify the software name and version (if more than one version is used please enter versions on separate lines).

Showing all 2 responses	
Spinsolve	951912-951894-101614904
Bruker ParaVision	951912-951894-102109484

9 What operating systems do your spectrometer computers run? (select all that apply)

9.a If you selected Linux, please specify the distribution (Debian, Fedora etc) and version.

Showing first 5 of 32 responses	
CentOS 5 and 7	951912-951894-101369602
CentOS	951912-951894-101370884
Centos 7	951912-951894-101397499
CentOS 5 CentOS 7	951912-951894-101524313
Red Hat	951912-951894-101550127

9.b If you selected Windows, please specify the version.

Showing first 5 of 25 responses	
WinXP	951912-951894-101370884
Windows 11	951912-951894-101524313
Win 10	951912-951894-101550127
7	951912-951894-101560777
Windows 10	951912-951894-101613960

9.c If you selected Mac OS, please specify the version.

Showing 1 response	
Monterey, Ventura	951912-951894-101614904

9.d If you selected Other, please specify the operating system and version.

Showing 1 response	
Centos	951912-951894-102079790

10 What type of NMR are the spectrometers in your facility equipped for? (select one)

11 Tell us about the users of your NMR facility. (select all that apply)

12 What types of NMR experiments do your users carry out? (select all that apply)

12.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 4 responses	
NMR of soft materials (gels, ionic liquids, deep eutectic solvents, polymers) HP-NMR	951912-951894-101690708
Reaction monitoring Molecular dynamics studies	951912-951894-101908122
Routine small molecule char. for inorganic and physical chemistry, metal organic chemistry	951912-951894-101968664
NMR in oriented media	951912-951894-102194221

13 On average, how many users does your facility have in a year?

14 Local users

Showing first 5 of 55 responses	
51-100	951912-951894-101369602
300	951912-951894-101397499
85	951912-951894-101401907
30	951912-951894-101524313
50	951912-951894-101550127

15 National users

Showing first 5 of 41 responses	
20	951912-951894-101524313
3	951912-951894-101550127
25	951912-951894-101559699
0	951912-951894-101560777
<10	951912-951894-101613960

16 Transnational users (EU-wide and world-wide)

Showing first 5 of 31 responses	
10	951912-951894-101524313
5	951912-951894-101550127
5	951912-951894-101559699
0	951912-951894-101560777
<10	951912-951894-101613960

17 Industrial users

Showing first 5 of 40 responses	
10	951912-951894-101369602
5	951912-951894-101397499
1	951912-951894-101401907
5	951912-951894-101524313
3	951912-951894-101550127

18 How do users of your NMR facility login to the spectrometers and do they have access to other users' data? (select all that apply)

18.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 9 responses	
Individual accounts with access to other users' files	951912-951894-101524313
Group of users (team of researchers) without access to other groups	951912-951894-101614904
industrial: personal departmental: per institute for paranoid people we sometimes make individual accounts lab course account for training students separate user accounts within IconNMR	951912-951894-101742975
We use in house developed NMR data management system. https://www.nomad-nmr.uk/	951912-951894-101890690
Individual accounts for research groups, all users of the same group share the account and have open access to the files of the group members but no access to the data of other research groups	951912-951894-101968664
group accounts: each research unit has its own account. Users of a same research unit can access the group data	951912-951894-102045678
Users from the same group account can submit samples on that account on the spectrometer but access to the same account users' files on an NMR server on the local network.	951912-951894-102074887
No access	951912-951894-102079790
Individual accounts managed by the technician of the NMR	951912-951894-102162958

19 Are different levels of spectrometer access provided for users with different levels of expertise?

20 Which of the following describe categories of users in your facility? (select all that apply)

20.a If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing 1 response

The facility provides support to research in different fields and industry however this experiments are carried out by the NMR technician or an expert user.	951912-951894-101690708
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21 If your facility has different categories of users, how is user expertise level assessed? (Please specify)

Showing first 5 of 38 responses	
We have specialist users, who are able to run their own experiments in TopSpin without the support of NMR staff. These users must: i) Convince NMR staff that they will be regular users of our NMR instrumentation; ii) Be running experiments that are not normally available on open-access instrumentation; and iii) Once trained/during training display a sufficient level of competence to run and NMR experiment with the assistance of NMR staff.	951912-951894-101397499
By the user during project deposition (for national and transnational access). All local users are considered as experts.	951912-951894-101524313
By the staff	951912-951894-101550127
-preset experiment on automats with limited paramters accessibels - preset experiment on manual spectrometers with all the power set - solid state specialist in the facility - letting them do until they ask question	951912-951894-101559699
training and evaluation	951912-951894-101560777

22 How is user NMR data kept secure and how do users access their data? (Please specify).

Showing first 5 of 44 responses	
Each research group has its own login, data gets copied via ICON-NMR to their data directories. Linux access rght only for this group and the facility manager. Users login to the data server via scp file client.	951912-951894-101369602
Each user is owner of her/his data and solely responsible for safekeeping their data. Data access is by some FTP program or USB stick.	951912-951894-101370884
Access is only possible through the local network infrastucture. For external users, data are usually transferred through cloud storage by the local operator.	951912-951894-101524313
Stored on internal HD with limited outside access. Access via OneDrive or USB. Alterantively, mailed by staff via email or filesender	951912-951894-101550127
via the LDAP of the school to connect on our server where the NMR data are stored	951912-951894-101559699

23 Prior to, during and since the Covid19 pandemic, did you provide remote access to one or more of the NMR spectrometers in your facility? By remote access, we mean that either: 1) users could directly operate the NMR spectrometer by remote login to the NMR spectrometer computer (direct remote access), or 2) users could communicate via a computer linkup (Zoom/Teams etc) or telephone with a local operator who controlled the NMR spectrometer based on the information provided by the remote user (assisted remote access), or 3) some other type of remote access.

23.a If you would like to provide more detailed information about your mode of remote spectrometer access then please fill in the text box.

No responses

23.b Why has remote access to spectrometers not been implemented in your facility? (select any that apply)

23.b.i If you selected Other, please specify:

Showing all 9 responses	
No professional IT resources to implement it.	951912-951894-101524313
We don't have ATMA (automatic tune and match), which is common in solid-state NMR. Nevertheless for samples in which experiments run for several days, it would be nice to change experimental parameters and start new experiments from anywhere.	951912-951894-101664309
Currently the users that require hands-on on the spectrometer are all of them local (university). External users what they do up to now is to sent the samples to the NMR lab and we provide the NMR measurements for them.	951912-951894-101728393
The lack of expertise of our end users made it impossible. We cannot trust them. They just know how to operate the instrument in automatic mode. Past experiences taught us they cannot have admin rights or autonomy to operate the magnet themselves for troubleshooting or anything outside the standard experiments in IconNMR. Also, there is a high turnover of students every year, so there is a small number of people who becomes confident to use the instrument. If anything, we would implement remote access for a selected group of people with different levels of access.	951912-951894-101890829
no ATMA probes, sample preparation challenges	951912-951894-101894250
In our experience running topspin remote needs very fast and broad internet resources which we do not always have	951912-951894-101968664
During the first lockdown, all labs were closed. With the following lockdown, a booking website was implemented allowing access to the lab, but for onsite users one per one. Sanitary measures were implemented (one user at a time ; use of hydro alcoholic gel)	951912-951894-102045678
Only NMR staff had access to the spectrometers and were running all the samples of users	951912-951894-102074887
The research process, which is the major source of the users/samples, has not stopped and onsite access was available with all safety precautions. Remote access would only be needed if no one would be able to come to work, but then there would be no samples to analyze.	951912-951894-102129042

23.c The aim of the Remote-NMR project is to develop a common framework for remote spectrometer access taking into account best practice across the EU/UK. Standardized training for remote access will also be put in place. Once this has been completed, would your NMR facility be interested in implementing remote spectrometer access?

43 If you have further information that you would like to provide, please enter this in the text box below.

Showing all 6 responses	
we run experiments under ISO 17025, which restricts spectrometer access remote access is restricted to the operators	951912-951894-101560777
As long as we cannot do "remote sample preparation", remote access would be of limited usefulness in our environment.	951912-951894-101908122
At the moment we see no need for remote access, but that may change, so "no" for the last 2 questions does not mean "never".	951912-951894-101968664
We have facilities that can provide the access to following measurements, specialties apart from routine measurements: 1. Dynamic Nuclear Polarisation. 2. Low temperature Magic-Angle Spinning at temperatures reaching 30 K. 3. Metabolomics. 4. In-operando or in-situ NMR for research related to energy materials, like battery materials, solar cells, etc.	951912-951894-102129570
I usually access the system remotely, on a daily basis, but for managing purposes. The system is equipped with an autosampler allowing for further experiments on the same sample, that can be performed remotely after analysis of the gathered spectra. I think the remote access can be readily implemented using any software for this purpose, as Anydesk.	951912-951894-102131754
implementation of remote access in our facility requires hiring a technician to handle samples and operate of spectrometers. Is it possible in this network?	951912-951894-102223422